

1 **Accretional soil formation in northern hemisphere loess regions - evidence from OSL-**
2 **dating of the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition from China, Europe and North**
3 **America**

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28 **Abstract**

29 Loess deposits intercalated by paleosols are detailed terrestrial archives of Quaternary climate
30 variability providing information on the global dust cycle and landscape dynamics. Their
31 paleoclimate significance is most often explored by quantifying the mineral magnetic properties
32 due to their sensitivity to local/regional hydroclimate variability. Detailed chronological
33 assessment of such regional proxy records around the climatic transitions allow a better
34 understanding of how regional records react to major global climatic transitions such as the
35 Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition.

36 First, logs of high-resolution magnetic susceptibility and its frequency dependence were used as
37 paleoclimatic proxies to define the environmental transition from the last glacial loess to the
38 current interglacial soil as reflected in nine loess-paleosol sequences across the northern
39 hemisphere, from the Chinese Loess Plateau, the southeastern European loess belt and the central

40 Great Plains, Nebraska, USA. Second, the onset of increase in their values above typical loess
41 values was used to assess the onset of, and developments during, the Pleistocene-Holocene
42 climatic transition.

43 High-resolution luminescence dating is applied on multiple grain-sizes (4-11 μm , 63-90 μm , 90-
44 125 μm) of quartz extracts from the same sample in order to investigate the timing of
45 Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition in the investigated sites.

46 The magnetic susceptibility signal shows a smooth and gradual increase for the majority of the
47 sites from the typical low loess values to the interglacial ones. The initiation of this increase,
48 interpreted as recording the initiation of the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition at each site,
49 was dated to 14-17.5 ka or even earlier. Our results highlight the need of combining
50 paleoclimatic proxies (magnetic susceptibility) with absolute dating when investigating the
51 Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition as reflected by the evolution of this proxy in order to
52 avoid chronostratigraphic misinterpretations in loess-paleosol records caused by simple pattern
53 correlation.

54 The detailed luminescence chronologies evidence the continuity of eolian mineral dust
55 accumulation regardless of glacial or interglacial global climatic regimes. Coupled with magnetic
56 susceptibility records it indicates that dust sedimentation and pedogenesis act simultaneously and
57 result in the formation of accretional Holocene soils in loess regions across the Northern
58 Hemisphere. The luminescence ages allowed the modelling of accumulation rates for the
59 Holocene soil which are similar for European, Chinese and U.S. loess sites investigated and vary
60 from 2 cm ka^{-1} to 9 cm ka^{-1} . While accretional pedogenesis has often been implicitly or explicitly
61 assumed in paleoclimatic interpretation of loess-paleosol sequences, especially in the Chinese

62 Loess Plateau, our luminescence data add direct evidence for ongoing sedimentation as soils
63 formed.

64 **Keywords: accretional soils, Pleistocene-Holocene transition, luminescence dating, quartz,**
65 **magnetic susceptibility**

66 **1. Introduction**

67 Loess-paleosol sequences (LPS) are mostly widespread across mid-latitudes forming the loess
68 belt of the Northern Hemisphere. They are considered quasi-continuous terrestrial archives of
69 Quaternary climate variability providing information on the global dust cycle and landscape
70 dynamics. The characteristic alternations of loess and paleosol horizon reflect the climatic
71 fluctuation between relatively dry-cool and warm-humid conditions linked to glacial-interglacial
72 climate variability. Their timing is often assumed synchronous with main trends in climate
73 variability seen in other archives such as marine and ice core records (**Bazin et al., 2013**) to
74 which LPS are often matched on an orbital scale of past climate variability (**Marković et al.,**
75 **2015; Zeeden et al., 2020**).

76 Well known interactions between atmosphere – biosphere – pedosphere documented in other
77 paleoclimatic records (**Clark et al., 2012; Stern and Lisiecki, 2014; Magyari et al., 2019**)
78 highlight the need for well-dated, high-resolution records. Detailed chronological assessment of
79 regional proxy records around the climatic transitions would allow better understanding of how
80 regional records react to major global climatic transitions such as the Pleistocene-Holocene
81 climatic transition.

82 To achieve this we extend our previous investigations on Southeastern European loess belt
83 (**Constantin et al., 2019**) to include other records from the region, as well as from the Chinese
84 Loess Plateau and the Great Plains, Nebraska, USA.

85 A less explored aspect in the study of loess-paleosol archives is the mechanism of soil formation
86 and its development in eolian landscapes (**Roberts, 2008**). Conceptual models for the
87 development of mineral magnetic records in soils and other pedogenic evidence of
88 paleoenvironments under different regimes of eolian sedimentation can be discussed in terms of
89 two end-members. These include extension of the pedogenetic processes downward into the
90 parent loess material from a relatively stable land surface or top-down pedogenesis, and
91 accretional or “up-building” soil formation in which the pedogenetic processes encompass the
92 sediment as it accumulates over time (**Almond and Tonkin, 1999; Kemp, 2001; Jacobs and**
93 **Mason, 2007; Schaetzl and Anderson, 2009; Jordanova and Jordanova, 2020; Rousseau et**
94 **al., 2021**). These categories represent the extreme ends of a continuum; however, exclusive “top-
95 down pedogenesis” is hardly realized in settings where dust was quasi-continuously deposited
96 over hundreds of thousands of years, even during the Holocene (**Albani et al., 2015; Longman**
97 **et al., 2017; Lehmkuhl et al., 2021**).

98 The degree to which paleosols developed primarily through top-down or accretional pedogenesis
99 is a crucial paleoclimate aspect of loess-paleosol records though often not discussed explicitly
100 (**Rousseau et al., 2017; Schaetzl et al., 2018**). Where dust accumulation and loess formation is
101 more or less continuous and accretional pedogenesis predominates, then at least some forms of
102 pedogenetic alteration—soil structure formation, organic matter accumulation, and magnetic
103 susceptibility enhancement, for example—can occur not long after the time of deposition. In this
104 situation, a pedogenically overprinted sedimentary archive and the record of magnetic

105 susceptibility or other paleoenvironmental proxies related to environmental changes and
106 pedogenesis can be interpreted essentially as a time series, the usual interpretation in loess-
107 paleosol studies. If dust accumulation is minimal for a significant period of time, then
108 pedogenetic horizons form in previously accumulated sediment resulting in top-down
109 pedogenesis that over time extends downward.

110 A straightforward argument in support of accretional pedogenesis at a given loess site is to show
111 that continuous dust accumulation has occurred under a wide range of climatic conditions, from
112 full-glacial to interglacial. Besides high-resolution dating constraints, stratigraphically consistent
113 records of paleo-environmental proxy parameters such as environmental magnetic susceptibility
114 and grain size would allow assessing the accretional character of the pedo-complex.

115 In the studied records, the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition is recorded by the broad
116 transition from last glacial loess into a prominent paleosol. We aim at assessing proxy variability
117 in several loess-paleosol records from the Northern Hemisphere loess belt, covering the
118 Pleistocene/Holocene climatic transition. We rely on luminescence dating of different grain-sizes
119 of quartz separates for assessing regional response to the critical Pleistocene/ Holocene climate
120 transition as recorded by loess deposits. We then compare our multi-site chronological data to
121 test for synchronicity of response within deposits worldwide, and with other key global records
122 of past climate variability. In interpreting each study site, we note evidence of all types in
123 support of accretional pedogenesis.

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128 **Figure 1.** Map of worldwide loess distribution modified after **Li et al. (2020)** provided by
 129 Yanrong Li. The investigated loess regions are indicated on the map. Right inset shows a close-
 130 up the Chinese Loess Plateau and the investigated loess sites CX: Caoxian, BCY: Baicaoyuan, as
 131 well as other sites discussed in text, LC: Luochuan (**Lu et al., 2013**), XC Huanxian (**Lu et al.,**
 132 **2006; Dong et al., 2015**). Left inset gives a close-up of the central and southeastern European
 133 loess belt and shows the investigated study sites PRI: Kurortne (**Tecsa et al., 2020a**), ROX:
 134 Roxolany (**Constantin et al., 2019**), MV: Mircea Voda (**Groza-Sacaciu et al., 2020**), RS:
 135 Ramnicu Sarat (**Constantin et al., 2019**), SM: Smederevo, MVS: Mošorin Veliki Surduk
 136 (**Constantin et al., 2019**).

137 **2. Sites**

138 This study gathers data from nine loess-paleosol sequences (LPS) across Europe, Asia, and
 139 North America (**Figures 1**). These include the Baicaoyuan and Caoxian LPS in the Chinese

140 Loess Plateau, Kuma in the loess-mantled High Plains in Nebraska, and Smederevo in Serbia
141 that are first discussed here. Other recently published records (**Constantin et al., 2019; Groza-**
142 **Sacaciu et al., 2020; Tecsă et al., 2020a**) such as Roxolany and Kurortne from the loess belt
143 north of the Black Sea, Ramnicu Sarat and Mircea Voda from the Lower Danube Basin loess,
144 and Mošorin Veliki Surduk from the Middle Danube basin loess are also included in this
145 overview. Details on luminescence sampling and stratigraphies are given in **Figures 2-10**.

146 *Sites from SE European loess belt*

147 The Kurortne LPS (45°54' N, 30°16' E) is located near Kurortne village (Odessa region,
148 Ukraine), at the Black Sea shore (**Figure 1, 2 and S2**). The Roxolany LPS (46.2° N, 30.5° E) is
149 located on the left bank of the Dniester estuary in southeastern Ukraine (**Figure 1, 3 and S3**).

150 The Mircea Voda LPS (48.3° N, 28.2° E) is situated on the Dobrogea loess plateau, in the
151 proximity of the Danube and the Black Sea (**Figure 1, 4, S1 and S4**). The Ramnicu Sarat outcrop
152 (45.5° N, 27.0° E; 160 m) is situated on the left bank of the Ramnicu Sarat river valley, at the
153 northern edge of the Lower Danube Basin loess (**Figure 1, 5, S1 and S5**).

154 The Mošorin Veliki Surduk LPS outcrops on the western slope of a 35 m deep gully, on the Titel
155 Plateau, Vojvodina, Serbia (**Figure 1, 6, S1 and S6**). The Smederevo site is an outcrop on the
156 uppermost terrace on the Danube valley in the south of the extensively investigated loess
157 plateaus in the Vojvodina region, Serbia (**Figure 1, 7, S1 and S7**).

158 At these SE European Loess Belt LPS, the darkest and most prominent A horizon caps the top of
159 a sedimentary section, with the appearance of a chernozem or similar soil typical of the steppe or
160 forest steppe environments where these sites occur.

KURORTNE

161 **Figure 2.** Kurortne site, Ukraine, SE Europe. To the left, the lithostratigraphic column and OSL sampling positions and the weighted
 162 average OSL ages (ka) on 4-11 μm, 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm quartz. To the right, the weighted average luminescence ages and the
 163 modeled ages as function of depth. The uncertainty of the modeled ages represents the overall uncertainty calculated according to
 164 **Aitken et al. (1985)**. Also shown, the variation of the frequency dependent ($\chi_{lf} - \chi_{hf}$) and low frequency (χ_{lf}) magnetic susceptibility
 165 signals with depth. The dashed lines mark the depth interval dated to 17.5 ka and 11.7 ka within the error limits of the modeled ages.

166 **Figure 3.** Roxolany site, Ukraine, SE Europe. To the left, the lithostratigraphic column and OSL sampling positions and the weighted
 167 average OSL ages (ka) on 4-11 μm , 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm quartz. To the right, the weighted average luminescence ages and the
 168 modeled ages as function of depth. The uncertainty of the modeled ages represents the overall uncertainty calculated according to
 169 **Aitken et al. (1985)**. Also shown, the variation of the frequency dependent ($\chi_{lf}-\chi_{hf}$) and low frequency (χ_{lf}) magnetic susceptibility
 170 signals with depth. The dotted lines mark the depth interval where a hiatus in OSL ages occurs. The short dashed lines indicate the
 171 depth interval dated to 17.5 ka within the error limits of the modeled ages.

MIRCEA - VODA

172 **Figure 4.** Mircea-Voda site, Romania, SE Europe. To the left, the lithostratigraphic column, OSL sampling positions and the weighted
 173 average OSL ages (ka) on 4-11 μm and 63-90 μm quartz. To the right, the weighted average luminescence ages and the modeled ages
 174 as function of depth. The uncertainty of the modeled ages represents the overall uncertainty calculated according to **Aitken et al.**
 175 **(1985)**. Also shown, the variation of the frequency dependent ($\chi_{lf}-\chi_{hf}$) and low frequency (χ_{lf}) magnetic susceptibility signals with
 176 depth. The dashed lines mark the depth interval dated to 17.5 ka and 11.7 ka within the error limits of the modeled ages.

177 **Figure 5.** Ramnicu Sarat site, Romania, SE Europe. To the left, the lithostratigraphic column, OSL sampling positions and the 63-90
 178 μm quartz OSL ages (ka). To the right, the luminescence ages and the modeled ages as function of depth. The uncertainty of the
 179 modeled ages represents the overall uncertainty calculated according to **Aitken et al. (1985)**. Also shown, the variation of the
 180 frequency dependent ($\chi_{lf}-\chi_{hf}$) and low frequency (χ_{lf}) magnetic susceptibility signals with depth. The dotted lines mark the depth
 181 interval dated to 11.7 ka within the error limits of the modeled ages.

MOSORIN

182 **Figure 6.** Mošorin Veliki Surduk site, Serbia, SE Europe. To the left, the lithostratigraphic column, OSL sampling positions and the
 183 weighted average OSL ages (ka) on 4-11 μm and 63-90 μm quartz. To the right, the weighted average luminescence ages and the
 184 modeled ages as function of depth. The uncertainty of the modeled ages represents the overall uncertainty calculated according to
 185 **Aitken et al. (1985)**. Also shown, the variation of the frequency dependent ($\chi_{lf} - \chi_{hf}$) and low frequency (χ_{lf}) magnetic susceptibility
 186 signals with depth. The dashed lines mark the depth interval dated to 17.5 ka within the error limits of the modeled ages.

SMEDEREVO

187 **Figure 7.** Smederevo site, Serbia, SE Europe. To the left, the lithostratigraphic column, OSL sampling positions and the 63-90 μm
 188 quartz OSL ages (ka). To the right, the luminescence ages and the modeled ages as function of depth. The uncertainty of the modeled
 189 ages represents the overall uncertainty calculated according to **Aitken et al. (1985)**. Also shown, the variation of the frequency
 190 dependent ($\chi_{lf}-\chi_{hf}$) and low frequency (χ_{lf}) magnetic susceptibility signals with depth. The dotted lines mark the depth interval dated to
 191 17.5 ka and 11.7 ka within the error limits of the modeled ages.

192 *Sites from the Chinese Loess Plateau*

193 Caoxian LPS (36°22'29.40" N, 104°37'18.19" E, 2081 m a.s.l.) is located near the Caoxian
194 village, Jingyuan county, Gansu Province, northwestern Loess Plateau (**Figure 1** and **S8**). The
195 Caoxian section is situated on the sixth terrace of the Yellow River in Jingyuan Basin. At this
196 section and others exposing the uppermost part of the loess-paleosol record on the Chinese Loess
197 Plateau (CLP), there is an upward gradation from typical loess through lighter, less strongly
198 expressed soil horizons to a dark, strongly expressed buried A horizon and then back to more
199 weakly developed horizons again (**Figure 8** and **S9**).

200 Baicaoyuan LPS (36°15'50.80" N, 105°08'05.21" E, 2050 m a.s.l.) is located in Huining County,
201 Gansu Province, in the northwest edge of the CLP (**Figure 1** and **S8**). In this section, there is an
202 upward progression from typical loess through horizons displaying progressively greater
203 pedogenic alteration, to a darker A horizon. (**Figure 9** and **S10**).

204 *Site from Great Plains loess, Nebraska, US*

205 Kuma site (90.48064 N, 101.39258 W) is located in the western part of the Great Plains loess
206 (**Figure 1**, **S1** and **S12**). Based on comparison with the nearby Wauneta (**Miao et al., 2007**) and
207 Enders (**Tecsa et al., 2020b**) LPS, the sequence here is correlated with the Pleistocene Peoria
208 Loess (typical unweathered loess), the Pleistocene to Holocene Brady Soil (a sequence of
209 transitional horizons grading up to a thick, dark A horizon), and the Holocene Bignell Loess
210 (lighter-colored zone at the top of the section) (**Figure 10** and **S12**). The Brady Soil has
211 previously been interpreted as an accretionary soil (**Mason et al., 2008**), in part because of the
212 clear evidence for dust input under both glacial and interglacial climates in this region, including
213 enhanced dust accumulation through much of the Holocene (**Miao et al., 2007**). The Bignell

214 **Figure 8.** Caoxian site, Chinese Loess Plateau. To the left, the lithostratigraphic column, OSL sampling positions and the 63-90 μm
 215 quartz OSL ages (ka). To the right, the luminescence ages and the modeled ages as function of depth. The uncertainty of the modeled
 216 ages represents the overall uncertainty calculated according to **Aitken et al. (1985)**. Also shown, the variation of low frequency (χ_{lf})
 217 magnetic susceptibility signals with depth. The dashed lines mark the depth interval dated to 17.5 ka and 11.7 ka within the error
 218 limits of the modeled ages.

219 **Figure 9.** Baicaoyuan site, Chinese Loess Plateau. To the left, the lithostratigraphic column, OSL sampling positions and the weighted
 220 average OSL ages (ka) on 4-11 μm and 63-90 μm quartz. To the right, the weighted average luminescence ages and the modeled ages
 221 as function of depth. The uncertainty of the modeled ages represents the overall uncertainty calculated according to **Aitken et al.**
 222 **(1985)**. Also shown, the variation of the low frequency (χ_{lf}) magnetic susceptibility signals with depth. The dashed lines mark the
 223 depth interval dated to 17.5 ka and 11.7 ka within the error limits of the modeled ages.

224 **Figure 10.** Kuma site, Nebraska, US. To the left, the lithostratigraphic column and OSL sampling positions and the weighted average
 225 OSL ages (ka) on 4-11 μm , 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm quartz. To the right, the weighted average luminescence ages and the modeled
 226 ages as function of depth. The uncertainty of the modeled ages represents the overall uncertainty calculated according to **Aitken et al.**
 227 **(1985)**. Also shown, the variation of the frequency dependent ($\chi_{lf}-\chi_{hf}$) and low frequency (χ_{lf}) magnetic susceptibility signals with
 228 depth. The dashed lines mark the depth interval dated to 11.7 ka within the error limits of the modeled ages.

229 Loess is much thicker at the Wauneta and Enders LPS because they are on the upwind edge of
230 loess plateaus where coarse dust that became Bignell Loess was probably eroded proximally
231 from older loess exposed on the plateau margin as well as from more distant sources. However,
232 the field-observed morphology of the Brady Soil is very similar at those sites and at Kuma, and
233 the stratigraphy of the Kuma site is more typical of large areas of the central Great Plains
234 (Mason et al., 2003; Jacobs and Mason, 2007).

235 **3. Methodology**

236 *3.1 Magnetic susceptibility sampling and measurements*

237 Magnetic susceptibility samples were collected from the same profile as the luminescence
238 samples and the continuous sampling resolution encompass 2 cm (for Kurortne, Roxolany,
239 Mircea Voda) or 5 cm (for Mošorin Veliki Surduk, Smederevo, Baicaoyuan, Caoxian and Kuma)
240 per sample, except for Ramnicu Sarat with samples collected 10 cm apart. For samples collected
241 from the Kurortne, Roxolany, Mošorin Veliki Surduk and Kuma sections, the volumetric
242 magnetic susceptibility was measured at frequencies of 300 Hz and 3000 Hz in a static field of
243 300 mA/m using a Magnon International VSM (sensitivity $\sim 10^{-7}$ SI) at University of Bayreuth,
244 Germany. For the samples from the Mircea Voda, Ramnicu Sarat and Smederevo sections the
245 magnetic susceptibility was measured at University of Bucharest, Romania with an AGICO
246 MFK1-FA Kappabridge (sensitivity $\sim 2 \times 10^{-8}$ SI) using a magnetic field of 200 A/m and
247 frequencies of 976 Hz and respectively 15616 Hz. Samples collected from the CLP sites were
248 measured using a Bartington MS2 Susceptibility Meter at the Peking University, China.

249 All data were corrected for drift and for the effect of holder and sampling boxes (weak
250 diamagnetism) and normalized to mass. Frequency dependence of magnetic susceptibility was

251 expressed as a mass-specific loss of susceptibility $\chi_{fd} = \chi_{lf} - \chi_{hf}$, where χ_{lf} and χ_{hf} are the magnetic
252 susceptibility measured at low and high frequency, respectively (**Dearing et al., 1996**).

253 *3.2 Luminescence dating*

254 *Sample collection and preparation*

255 Luminescence samples were collected to closely bracket the transition between the loess unit
256 (L1) and the Holocene soil (S0) and the development of S0 soil, as identified visually in the
257 field. The L1/S0 transition was tentatively identified as the visual boundary between proper loess
258 and the overlying humus rich (A1 horizon) S0 soil – the transitional zone would refer to the
259 interval encompassing the genetic horizons (other than A1) of S0 that are clearly visible at all
260 sites. Rather than denoting a sharp boundary, the L1/S0 transition is marked in all sites by a
261 transitional horizon encompassing clear litho/pedostratigraphic variability as seen in **Figures 2-**
262 **10**.

263 Luminescence samples were collected at high resolution, at intervals varying from 5 cm to 30 cm
264 in between sample and for each LPS the number of samples judged necessary to include the full
265 record of the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition, was determined based on litho- and
266 pedostratigraphy. At some sites such as Caoxian and Kuma sites, more widely spaced samples,
267 up to 1 m apart, were used to extend the chronology into underlying loess or overlying soil units.
268 Sampling depths are given in **Supplementary Tables S1-9**.

269 The material was collected by hammering stainless steel cylinders (6 cm in diameter and 20 cm
270 in length) perpendicularly onto the freshly cleaned vertical profiles (**Figures S2-7, S9-10** and
271 **S12** – photos of the sampling profiles). The sealed tubes were opened under subdued red light at
272 Babeş-Bolyai University luminescence laboratory, Cluj-Napoca, Romania. The material at both

273 ends of the tubes was removed and used for gamma spectrometry measurements. From the
274 remaining material in the inner part of the tubes quartz of different grain-sizes was extracted for
275 luminescence measurements. In the first step, the bulk material was treated for several days with
276 HCl (35% concentration) followed by H₂O₂ (30% concentration) in order to remove the
277 carbonates and organic matter, respectively. The resulting material consisting of an
278 undifferentiated polymineral mixture was wet sieved through a 63- μ m mesh to separate between
279 the fine and medium (<63 μ m) and coarse fractions as they require different preparation
280 procedures. The material with a diameter larger than 63 μ m was further sieved to separate the
281 63-90 μ m and 90-125 μ m. It was enriched in quartz through a two-step density separation by
282 centrifugation in a heavy liquid solution containing sodium metatungstate Na₆[H₂W₁₂O₄₀] x H₂O.
283 The lighter material (such as K-feldspars) was separated from quartz and plagioclase grains by
284 centrifugation using 2.62 g/cm³ density while heavy minerals such as zircons and apatite were
285 isolated using 2.75 g/cm³ density. The resulting mixture of quartz and plagioclase feldspars was
286 treated with HF (40 % concentration) for 40 min in order to dissolve the latter and to etch away
287 the outer layer of quartz grains penetrated by alpha radiation. A rinse with HCl (10%
288 concentration) for 60 min dissolved the fluorides precipitated during the HF treatment. The
289 remaining quartz extracts were dry sieved to obtain the 63-90 μ m and 90-125 μ m, fractions. For
290 measurement, the coarse quartz grains were fixed in a monolayer on stainless steel disks (9 mm
291 in diameter) using silicone spray.

292 The polymineral mixture material with a diameter smaller than 63 μ m was processed to obtain
293 the 4-11 μ m quartz fraction by velocity settling in Atterberg cylinders using Stokes law followed
294 by a 10 day digestion in H₂SiF₆ (concentration 35%) and density separation by centrifugation in

295 distilled water. For measurement the aliquots were prepared by settling 2 mg of quartz on
296 aluminium discs (9 mm in diameter).

297 *Equivalent dose measurements*

298 Equivalent dose measurements were carried out using TL/OSL Risø DA-20 readers (**Bøtter-**
299 **Jensen et al., 2010**), equipped with classic or automated detection and stimulation head (DASH)
300 (**Lapp et al., 2015**). The luminescence signals were detected through 7.5 mm thick Hoya U-340
301 filters placed in front of an EMI 9235QA or PDM 9107Q-AP-TTL-03 photomultipliers,
302 depending on the reader type. Irradiations were performed using build-in $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ (beta
303 irradiation) sources calibrated using calibration quartz provided by the Nordic Laboratory for
304 Luminescence Dating.

305 The equivalent doses were measured using the Single Aliquot Regenerative dose (SAR) protocol
306 (**Murray and Wintle, 2000; 2003**). The quartz luminescence emission was stimulated with blue
307 light emitting diodes for 40 s at 125 °C and the net CW-OSL signal was isolated from the first
308 0.304 s of luminescence emission minus a background assessed from the 1.69-2.03 s of
309 luminescence emission. The OSL response to a test dose of 17 Gy was used to correct for
310 sensitivity changes in all investigations presented in this study, except for the case of equivalent
311 dose determination of very young samples ($D_e < 5$ Gy), when a test dose of 4 Gy was employed.
312 A preheat temperature of 220 °C for 10 s and a cutheat of 180 °C were employed. At the end of
313 each SAR cycle a high-temperature bleach for 40 s at 280 °C was performed by stimulation with
314 blue diodes (**Murray and Wintle, 2003**). Any possible quartz contamination with feldspars was
315 monitored through exposure to IR diodes in the IR depletion test (**Duller et al., 2003**) employed
316 on each aliquot measured. The performance of the SAR protocol was evaluated using the

317 standard intrinsic tests (Recycling and Recuperation ratios). The acceptance criteria were 10 %
318 deviation from unity for the Recycling and IR depletion ratios and a maximum of 3 % of the
319 natural signal for the Recuperation ratio. We have used similar measurement conditions for all
320 luminescence samples investigated in this study.

321 *Annual dose measurements*

322 For annual dose measurements, the material was dried and finely ground before being sealed in
323 the gamma spectrometry measurement tubes and left for one month to allow ^{222}Rn achieve
324 secular equilibrium with the ^{238}U series. Radionuclide activity concentrations were determined
325 based on high resolution gamma spectrometry using a hyper pure germanium well detector. The
326 conversion factors reported by **Guérin et al. (2011)** were used to derive the annual dose rates.
327 The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the beta and gamma radiations for coarse
328 grains as well as the contribution from alpha radiations in the case of fine grains. Adopted alpha
329 efficiency factor was 0.04 ± 0.02 (**Rees-Jones, 1995**) to correct for the lower efficiency of alpha
330 radiation in inducing luminescence for 4-11 μm quartz. Beta attenuation and etching factors used
331 for 63–90 μm and 90–125 μm quartz were 0.94 ± 0.05 and 0.92 ± 0.05 , respectively (**Mejdahl,**
332 **1979**). An internal dose rate of 0.010 ± 0.002 Gy/ka was considered (**Vandenberghé et al.,**
333 **2008**). The contribution of cosmic radiation was estimated following the equation published by
334 **Prescott and Hutton (1994)**. To correct for the attenuation effect on the absorbed dose by the
335 quartz grains, induced by the water surrounding the minerals in the loess matrix, estimation of
336 the average water content during burial is required. For this we took into consideration the
337 difference between the “as found” and the oven dried weight of material with a relative error of
338 25% as well as information on past humidity variation in other sites in the investigated regions.

339 The values for radionuclide concentrations as well as the total dose rates for all samples
340 discussed in this paper are found in **Tables S1-9**.

341 **3.3 Modeling of luminescence ages and accumulation rates**

342 For generating age-depth models, we used the ADMin software (**Zeeden et al., 2018**). This age-
343 depth Bayesian modelling approach makes no assumptions on accumulation rates, but assumes
344 luminescence ages and their uncertainties to be correct. Initially, the method separates the overall
345 uncertainty into a random and systematic part; here a separation based on luminescence
346 uncertainties (**Table S1-S9**) is used.

347 For the samples where one set of ages on different quartz grain-size fractions was reported, we
348 calculated the overall uncertainty by combining in quadrature the random and systematic
349 components (**Aitken, 1985, Appendix B**). On multiple grain-sizes of quartz, we determined the
350 overall random and overall systematic uncertainty as well as the overall uncertainty on the
351 weighted average age according to **Aitken (1985, Appendix B)**. For deriving accumulation
352 rates, we used the random uncertainty only. In addition, we used the computer code from **Zeeden**
353 **et al. (2018)**, but adjusted it to also output the individual Monte Carlo sampling chains. From
354 these, the accumulation rate and related uncertainty was determined. This allows for somewhat
355 more confined accumulation rate models, compared to using only the uncertainty of (modeled)
356 ages.

357 **4. Results**

358 *4.1. Luminescence characteristics and equivalent doses*

359 All quartz samples investigated emitted a luminescence signal during exposure to blue LEDs for
360 40 s at 125 °C, which decayed rapidly with stimulation time. Representative luminescence decay
361 curves of each grain-size fraction investigated are compared with those on calibration quartz
362 supplied by the Nordic Luminescence Laboratory (**Figure S13 insets**). It can be seen that their
363 shapes are indistinguishable thus indicating that the sampled luminescence emission used for
364 equivalent dose determination is dominated by the fast luminescence component. This is that part
365 of the luminescence emission that bleaches first and very rapidly upon light exposure. This
366 increases the likelihood that no significant residual signal from previous erosion and
367 transportation cycles affects the measured luminescence signal, a prerequisite for applying the
368 SAR protocol (**Murray and Wintle, 2000**).

369 The equivalent doses were determined by interpolating the sensitivity corrected natural OSL
370 signal onto the laboratory dose-response curve constructed for each aliquot. Representative SAR
371 luminescence dose-response curves are illustrated in **Figure S13** for individual aliquots of fine
372 (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm and 90-125 μm) grained quartz from Baicaoyuan, Caoxian and
373 Kuma samples. The intrinsic tests of the SAR protocol have been successfully passed as it is
374 demonstrated by the overlap of Recycling and IR depletion points and their corresponding
375 regeneration points and by the fact that the laboratory dose response curve passes close to the
376 origin of the axes.

377 We have investigated the influence of the temperature of the preheat, carried out prior to the
378 OSL signal read-out, on the measured equivalent dose using samples from Roxolany, Ramnicu
379 Sarat, Mošorin, Baicaoyuan and Kuma sites. As seen in **Figure S14** the equivalent doses are
380 similar for preheat temperatures ranging from 200-240 °C.

381 We used the combination of preheat for 10 s at 220 °C with cutheat to 180 °C for the dose
382 recovery test and the given irradiation dose approximated the equivalent dose, as in the
383 investigations on previously published sites. The SAR protocol accurately measured known
384 irradiation doses given prior to any heating treatments (**Figure S15**). Thus, the combination of
385 preheat for 10 s at 220 °C with cutheat to 180 °C used to measure all equivalent doses, except for
386 the samples in Mošorin Veliki Surduk, where slightly lower temperatures were used (**Constantin**
387 **et al., 2019**). The equivalent doses and the number of aliquots used for averaging are given in
388 **Tables S1-9** for all the investigated sites.

389 Because we are dating samples collected from soil or from the loess-soil transition using
390 luminescence method we investigate the degree to which post-depositional processes such as
391 grain mixing due to bioturbation might affect the accuracy of the measured equivalent doses and
392 consequently that of the ages.

393 Luminescence ages that decrease steadily upward through a soil are consistent with ongoing
394 sedimentation and accretional soil development. However, forms of mixing such as bio- or
395 cryoturbation can potentially also yield similar luminescence age trends through the downward
396 transport of soil exposed to light at the ground surface. The factors controlling the depth and
397 effectiveness of soil mixing processes and resulting trends of apparent luminescence age remain
398 poorly understood (**Gray et al., 2020**). A test for bioturbation or other mixing processes using
399 luminescence measurements can be made by investigating the degree of spread in equivalent
400 doses data beyond that expected based on individual equivalent dose uncertainties (i.e.,
401 overdispersion) (**Bateman et al., 2007; Galbraith and Roberts, 2012; Gliganic et al., 2015;**
402 **Hanson et al., 2015; Constantin et al., 2019**). If there is not much more scatter in soil than in
403 underlying loess, indicating relatively little mixing, this strengthens the assumption that a steady

404 upward decrease in ages through a soil mainly reflects ongoing dust accumulation and
405 accretional pedogenesis. In addition, limited evidence of mixing strengthens confidence in age
406 models within the soils and accumulation rates calculated from those age models.

407 We have quantified the spread in the equivalent doses on the Baicaoyuan sample BCY 1.2,
408 collected from the transition from last glacial loess to Holocene soil (**Fig. S16**), by measuring 51
409 aliquots of the 63-90 μm quartz separate and by determining the overdispersion calculated from
410 the Central Age Model (**Galbraith et al., 1999**). As seen in the radial plot in **Figure S16**, 71% of
411 the measured equivalent doses agree within 2-sigma uncertainty with the mean equivalent dose.
412 The overdispersion calculated from the Central Age Model (**Galbraith et al., 1999**) is 14%. We
413 interpret these values as normal as natural samples of quartz rarely yield equivalent dose
414 estimates that are statistically concordant with respect to their within-aliquot standard errors
415 (**Galbraith and Roberts, 2012**). Even in the absence of complicating factors such as post-
416 depositional mixing there is commonly 10-20% overdispersion among equivalent dose estimates
417 from single aliquots (**Galbraith and Roberts, 2012; Constantin et al; 2019**).

418 We also constructed radial plots for 63-90 μm quartz equivalent doses measured on soil and
419 loess samples from Kuma LPS (**Figure S16**). For the soil sample KUM 1.4, 55% of equivalent
420 doses agree within 2-sigma uncertainty to the mean equivalent dose while for the KUM 1.7
421 sample collected from the transition from loess to the Holocene soil this value is slightly lower at
422 42%. The overdispersion calculated for these two samples are 6% and 9% respectively.

423 In **Table S10** we present scatter data expressed as relative standard error, RSD (%), and
424 overdispersion, OD (%), in multigrain aliquots of 63-90 μm quartz extracted from both soil and
425 loess samples from the Kurortne, Mircea Voda, Caoxian, Baicaoyuan and Kuma sites. Together

426 with the previously published data on the Roxolany, Ramnicu Sarat and Mošorin sites (see
427 **Figure S7** in **Constantin et al. (2019)**) we observe that the RSD and OD values are generally
428 around or below 20% with the exception of some uppermost soil samples where the observation
429 can be explained by modern agricultural disturbance. Based on this we conclude that a small
430 change in scatter in equivalent doses between loess and soil samples occurs only in some cases.
431 This assures us that post-depositional mixing does not significantly affect the chronological
432 results. The lack of evidence for substantially greater mixing in soils as compared to loess
433 supports interpretation of the age trends within the soils as primarily recording ongoing
434 sedimentation rather than effects of bioturbation. As further support for this interpretation, most
435 of the Holocene ages in these LPS fall within subsurface soil horizons, not in a thick and
436 homogeneous A horizon consistent with deep mixing from the surface downward (**Figures 2-**
437 **10**). In the Kurortne, Mircea Voda, Ramnicu Sarat, Baicaoyuan, and Kuma LPS, Holocene ages
438 fall along age-depth trends of relatively consistent slope across multiple distinctly different
439 horizons (**Figures 2, 4, 5, 10**), also more readily explained by sedimentation than by deep
440 mixing. Finally, the ages that are critical for many of our interpretations are within or even below
441 the transitional lower horizons of soils, not in near-surface horizons where bioturbation is likely
442 to be most effective.

443 *4.2. OSL ages*

444 Luminescence dating for this study was performed using up to three grain-size classes (4-11 μm ,
445 63-90 μm , 90-125 μm) of quartz extracted from the same sample. Such an approach is rare and
446 time-consuming but can reduce the random uncertainty of the age of a sample. Quartz grains in
447 multiple size fractions can be considered independent dosimeters, yielding multiple ages for the
448 same sample. This is due to the difference in the targeted grain diameter which, in turn

449 influences the degree of attenuation and absorption of alpha, beta and gamma radiation that form
450 the natural radioactive field surrounding the grain. The small diameter of fine grains of quartz (4-
451 11 μm) allows alpha radiation to pass through the entire grain while the coarser material (> 63
452 μm) fully attenuates the alpha irradiation within the outer layer of the grain which is then etched
453 away in the sampling preparation stage. In addition, the natural reduction in size of the fine
454 quartz grains likely occurred over many cycles of erosion, transport and deposition and
455 consequently irradiation and bleaching cycles that sensitize the grains.

456 With that background, by taking the weighted average of the luminescence dates obtained from
457 multiple grain-size fractions of a single sample, which are assumed to be coeval, the overall
458 random uncertainty can be reduced (**Aitken (1985, Appendix B)**). The contribution of the
459 random sources of uncertainty to the individual luminescence ages is a measure of their
460 precision. Thus by using weighted average ages from a suite of quartz grain sizes we aim at
461 obtaining a more precise age of the dated sedimentary context.

462 **Figures 2-10** show the luminescence chronologies as well as the modeled ages obtained for all
463 the sites investigated. Individual luminescence ages on each grain-size fraction of quartz and the
464 weighted average age calculated following **Aitken (1985) Appendix B** are presented in **Tables**
465 **S1-9**. Uncertainties on the individual ages were calculated based on the error assessment system
466 described by **Aitken and Alldred (1972)** and **Aitken (1976)**.

467 The systematic uncertainties on the individual ages for the fine grains amount to 8-10% while for
468 coarse grains vary from 6% to 8%. The main sources of systematic errors are the estimates of the
469 uncertainties associated with the time-averaged water content, alpha efficiency, and beta
470 attenuation factors.

471 The random uncertainty represents a measure of the internal consistency of the optical ages. For
472 coarse grains, they extended to 9% except for some uppermost soil samples where the
473 contribution increases up to 13-33%. In the case of the fine grains, the random error varies up to
474 6-8%.

475 Following **Aitken (1985, Appendix B)** we calculated weighted averages on fine and coarse
476 quartz ages (see **Tables S1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 9, 10**). The total uncertainty associated with the weighted
477 average age was calculated by first quantifying the random and the systematic components and
478 by propagating them in quadrature.

479 In this way the contribution of the random uncertainty to the overall uncertainty in the weighted
480 average age was reduced to 2-3% except in the case of four samples where the contribution
481 ranged from 4-7%. We obtained an overall uncertainty in the weighted average ages ranging
482 from 6-9%. To conclude, by weighting the fine and coarse quartz ages resulted in a decrease of
483 2% up to 6% in the total uncertainty of the age estimates.

484 **5. Dating of magnetic susceptibility enhancement using optically stimulated luminescence**

485 The magnetic properties of loess-paleosols such as mass specific low-field magnetic
486 susceptibility (χ_{lf}) and its dependence on the frequency of the applied field (χ_{fd}) are widely used
487 for disentangling the intensity of soil forming processes, as well as the chemical weathering of
488 primary loess. The χ_{fd} is also a highly diagnostic proxy for the exclusively pedogenetically
489 formed fraction of ferrimagnetic minerals (**Maher et al., 2003**).

490 The pedogenic enhancement of the magnetic susceptibility is an instantaneous syn- to long-term
491 post-depositional process formed in loess environments depending on the character of soil
492 formation governed by the continuum between accretional and top-down pedogenesis. It is

493 controlled in a complex way by climate through precipitation, temperature, and
494 evapotranspiration rate, reflecting long-term shifts variability in soil humidity (e.g. **Maher and**
495 **Thompson, 1994, 1995; Orgeira and Compagnucci, 2006; Orgeira et al., 2011; Song et al.,**
496 **2014; Hu et al., 2015**). The latter is controlled by wind, temperature, vegetation and local
497 conditions. As such, the trends in χ_{lf} and χ_{fd} are often regarded as reliable paleoclimate proxies
498 for inferring local hydroclimate variability (e.g. **Maher and Thompson, 1994, 1995; Schaetzl et**
499 **al., 2018**).

500 A gradual increase in magnetic susceptibility values, along with other evidence of
501 synsedimentary pedogenesis, marks the transition from the Last Glacial loess to the Holocene
502 soil in most of the loess-paleosol sections from the Danube Basin and Black Sea coast in Eastern
503 Europe (e.g. **Marković et al., 2015; Necula et al., 2015; Jordanova and Jordanova, 2020**),
504 Chinese Loess Plateau (e.g. **Maher et al., 2003; Dong et al., 2015**) and Great Plains (Nebraska,
505 United States) (e.g. **Tecsa et al., 2020b**).

506 Interpretation and dating of this trend of magnetic susceptibility depends in part on the
507 assumption that accretional pedogenesis predominated at all of these sites. The luminescence
508 ages at the LPS that were studied, in combination with tests for sediment mixing at selected sites,
509 are consistent with relatively continuous sediment accumulation into the Holocene. In addition,
510 pedostratigraphic evidence in LPS of the Chinese Loess Plateau and Great Plains records
511 ongoing Holocene dust accumulation forming lighter-colored zones above darker, better
512 developed soil horizons. This ongoing accumulation across the Pleistocene-Holocene transition,
513 though at varying rates, satisfies a key requirement for accretionary pedogenesis. In the SE
514 European Loess Belt LPS, pedostratigraphic evidence does not clearly support the ongoing dust
515 accumulation indicated by the luminescence ages, but in that setting, accumulating dust could

516 readily have been incorporated into thick upbuilding A horizons. Finally, it is also worth
517 emphasizing that the initial increase of magnetic enhancement is deep enough in these profiles
518 that it is unlikely to result from top down pedogenesis contemporaneous with development of the
519 overlying better-developed horizons. Considering only soils where top down pedogenesis is
520 likely to predominate, the magnitude and depth of magnetic enhancement vary with climate,
521 parent material, and soil age; however, in latest Pleistocene to Holocene nonaccretional soils in
522 semiarid climates it appears to be largely confined to the uppermost few tens of cm (**Singer and**
523 **Fine, 1989; Quinton et al., 2011**).

524 Assuming accretional pedogenesis, the simplest explanation of a gradual, smooth upward
525 increase in magnetic susceptibility is that it records a gradually more humid and warmer climate
526 increasing the degree of magnetic susceptibility enhancement and pedogenesis in general. Field
527 observations at some study sites reveal increasing evidence of pedogenesis associated with
528 increasing magnetic susceptibility, including redder hues and progressively darker colors
529 probably reflecting greater organic matter content (**Figures 2-10**). At other sites the initial
530 increase in magnetic susceptibility precedes evidence of incipient pedogenesis that is clearly
531 visible in the field.

532 It should also be considered whether a decreasing accumulation rate at many of the study sites
533 contributes to the trends of increasing magnetic susceptibility and increasing field evidence of
534 pedogenesis (accumulation rates are discussed in more detail below). Slower accumulation
535 means that the accumulating sediment is kept within the near-surface zone of most effective
536 pedogenesis for more time (**Roberts., 2008; Schaetzl and Anderson, 2009**). This competition
537 with sedimentation should be especially important for many relatively slow pedogenetic
538 processes, but we assume that magnetic susceptibility enhancement to the extent observed early

539 in the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition at these sites can occur relatively quickly, so
540 changing accumulation rate would have only minor effect on it. In any case, a decreased
541 accumulation rate, especially when observed across a large region, will itself often reflect
542 climatic change reducing rates of dust emission and transport.

543 A sharper increase in magnetic susceptibility clearly could record a response to rapid climate
544 change (**Landais et al., 2018**) but could have at least two other explanations: There is a
545 discontinuity in the record reflecting erosion or lack of sedimentation, or the weathering front
546 progressed downwards in a period of intense pedogenesis during very slow eolian dust input that
547 allowed for enhanced top-down soil formation (**Jordanova and Jordanova, 2020; Roberts,**
548 **2008; Schaetzl and Anderson, 2009**). The later would seemingly cause an age offset in case
549 pedogenesis (i.e., magnetic susceptibility enhancement) alone is taken as paleoclimate proxy.

550 Since in loess studies there is no established approach of constraining the interval in the
551 magnetic susceptibility record that reflects the Pleistocene-Holocene boundary we adopted an
552 approach similar to **Stern and Lisiecki (2014)**. We observe the variation of the χ_{fd} values over
553 the transition from the Last Glacial maximum (LGM) to Holocene through two temporal
554 reference points: 17.5 ka for Termination 1, as the Pleistocene-Holocene transition occurring in
555 benthic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record (**Stern and Lisiecki, 2014**), and 11.7 ka for the chronological boundary as
556 defined in ice-core records (**Rasmussen et al., 2014; Walker et al., 2019**).

557 Based on these considerations, for each studied LPS we have determined the depth where the χ_{fd}
558 values increase significantly and continuously (**Figs. 2-10**) compared to those values that
559 characterize the late glacial loess (or where available LGM loess). From the age model obtained
560 for each LPS we estimate the age corresponding to that depth and interpret that age as the onset

561 of the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition, assuming that accretionary pedogenesis has
562 predominated at these sites and that the OSL chronology is not substantially affected by soil
563 mixing processes. We also consider how the timing of the climatic transition compares to well-
564 established and dated boundaries from ice-core and marine records, specifically 17.5 ka for
565 Termination 1, as the Pleistocene-Holocene boundary as identified in benthic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records
566 (**Stern and Lisiecki, 2014**) and 11.7 ka for the Pleistocene-Holocene boundary as defined in ice-
567 core records (**Rasmussen et al., 2014; Walker et al., 2019**).

568 *SE European Loess Belt sites*

569 At Kurortne (KR), located the northern sea-shore of the Black Sea in Ukraine, from the base of
570 the sequence the χ_{fd} increases very slowly up to ~17 ka and accelerates in two steps after 17.5 ka
571 and around 11.7 ka until it reaches a constant level after 4 ka (**Figure 2**). The onset of
572 enhancement in magnetic susceptibility is thus identified prior to the loess-soil transition
573 identified visually in the field that was dated around 11.7 ka. At Roxolany (ROX) on Dniester
574 estuary in Ukraine, the χ_{fd} values are relatively stable up to around 17.5 ka when they start to
575 increase slowly until around 15 ka at 0.68 m depth (**Figure 3**). A very sharp increase in χ_{fd} values
576 occurs between 0.63 m and 0.55 m but an age gap of ~ 5 ka is indicated by OSL ages over this
577 depth interval as well as by the sharp and undulating boundary. For the soil horizons younger
578 than 8.6 ± 0.7 ka, the χ_{fd} values remain stable. The onset of increase in χ_{fd} values (~ 17.5 ka)
579 precedes the loess-soil transition identified in the field here as well (**Figure S3**).

580 One explanation for the sharp transition of χ_{fd} and age gap can be the effect of top-down soil
581 development at a time of minimal dust accumulation (**Roberts, 2008**). Yet the intensity of both
582 χ_{f} and χ_{fd} signals in Roxolany samples are lower than all other European sites investigated here

583 as well as reported in the literature (**Marković et al., 2015; Panaiotu et al., 2001**), inconsistent
584 with a period of substantial top-down pedogenesis. The age gap suggests instead an erosional
585 event and a gap in the record corresponding to the sharp χ_{fd} increase. Accumulation rates for the
586 Holocene soil horizons younger than 8.6 ± 0.7 ka add support to this interpretation. (see **Section**
587 **6**). An alternative, less likely explanation could be intense top-down pedogenesis including
588 substantial mixing in the soil above the age gap, making ages obtained there too young, and
589 downward extension of a weathering front producing the sharp increase in magnetic
590 susceptibility. However, intense mixing is not supported by the luminescence data.

591 In Mircea Voda site (MV), Dobrogea loess plateau, Lower Danube basin, starting from the base
592 of the sampled loess unit dated around 20 ka, the χ_{fd} values display a tendency to increase slowly
593 up to 11.7 ka after which the increase is more accelerated (**Figure 4**). The χ_{fd} values remain
594 constant after 5 ka for the uppermost 0.35 cm of the profile. It is worth noting that in Mircea
595 Voda, the onset of increase in χ_{fd} values also occurs prior to the loess-soil transition identified in
596 the field which is dated around 17.5 ka. A smooth increase in χ_{fd} values is seen along the loess-
597 soil transition in the Ramnicu Sarat site (RS) from the northern edge of the Lower Danube Basin
598 (**Figure 5**). Due to strong scatter in OSL ages dated to before 12 ka we can only conclude that
599 the χ_{fd} values are already significantly high around 12 ka. Also at this depth (130 cm) the
600 transition between loess and soil horizon was visually identified (**Figure 5 and S5**).

601 In Mošorin Veliki Surduk site (MVS), Titel loess plateau in the Middle Lower Danube basin, the
602 χ_{fd} values increase slowly and smoothly up to 14 ka (**Figure 6**). The rate of growth accelerates
603 around 11.7 ka and continues to increase until around 1.2 ka. The transition from loess to soil
604 identified visually in the field is dated around 14 ka (**Figure S6**). Smederevo site, along the
605 Danube river in Serbia, displays a rapid increase in χ_{fd} values much earlier than in all other sites,

606 before 21 ka, that continues at a relatively steady rate until 7.8 ± 0.8 ka, after which a decreasing
607 trend is observed (**Figure 7**). Please note an age difference of ~ 15 ka between 0.7 and 0.6 m (37
608 ± 3 ka and 21 ± 2 ka, respectively) at the depth interval where the rapid increase of χ_{fd} values is
609 observed and where the loess-soil transition has been identified in the field (**Figure S7**).

610 A common feature of these LSP investigated in the SE European Loess Belt is a slow increase in
611 magnetic susceptibility beginning before other clear evidence of pedogenesis, and well below the
612 most strongly expressed Holocene soil horizons. That is, relatively minor magnetic susceptibility
613 enhancement provides an early indication of the changing environment, before effects of other
614 pedogenetic processes are evident.

615 *Chinese Loess Plateau sites*

616 For Caoxian, NW Chinese Loess Plateau, the χ_{lf} values are constant until 3.5 m, dated at 15 ka,
617 after which they start to increase very slowly. From around 11.7 ka until ~ 3 ka at 1.725 m depth
618 the increase is accelerated, after which the values remain stable until 0.3 ka at 0.725 m (**Figure**
619 **8**). The visual loess-soil transition as identified in the field around 3 m has been dated to around
620 14 ka (**Figure 8** and **S9**). For Baicaoyuan (BCY), also from NW Chinese Loess Plateau the χ_{lf}
621 values are constant from 17 ka until a sharp increase starting at 11.7 ka up to a stable level
622 around 7 ka; there is an abrupt fluctuation early in this sharp increase (**Figure 9**). Prior to 11.7 ka
623 the intensity of the magnetic susceptibility signals are similar to those of Late Glacial loess in
624 Caoxian site but after 11.7 ka they are much higher, which indicates more intense pedogenesis at
625 the Baicaoyuan site. In the context of the NW-SE gradient in the intensity of the magnetic
626 susceptibility signal in soils across the Chinese Loess Plateau (**Maher et al., 2003; Dong et al.,**
627 **2015**) the maximum χ_{lf} values obtained for Baicaoyuan are rather common for the sites located in

628 the NW Chinese Loess Plateau. Across the depth interval (1.175-1.025 m) where the onset of
629 sudden increase in χ_{lf} is identified, three OSL samples indicate continuous dust deposition. The
630 three OSL samples above this interval also indicate ongoing loess sedimentation into the late
631 Holocene. Taken together, these observations cast doubt on interpretations of the abrupt increase
632 as either the result of an erosional event or a weathering front developed under intense top-down
633 pedogenesis. The maximum χ_{lf} values at Baicaoyuan do not indicate unusually intense
634 pedogenesis for the region of this site and OSL ages support ongoing sedimentation rather than
635 long-lasting stability of the land surface which led to top-down pedogenesis. With that
636 background, the abrupt χ_{lf} increase may simply record a particularly strong response of magnetic
637 susceptibility to climatic change around 11.7 ka. The transition from loess to soil as identified in
638 the field around 1.3 m is dated at ~ 14 ka, a few cm below the depth where the onset of the
639 increase in χ_{lf} occurs (**Figure S10**). Thus, at both the Chinese Loess Plateau LPS, the initial
640 increase of magnetic susceptibility coincides with or is slightly above other evidence of
641 pedogenesis in the lowest part of the Holocene soil.

642 *Great Plains loess, United States*

643 In Kuma site (KUM), Nebraska, for the lowermost 1.4 m of loess the OSL ages do not increase
644 with depth and scatter around 13-14 ka (**Figure 10**), a common observation in the uppermost late
645 Pleistocene Peoria Loess in western Nebraska, and probably reflecting very high accumulation
646 rates (**Roberts et al., 2003; Mason et al., 2008**). The χ_{fd} values remain relatively constant with
647 small variations until the upper part of this depth interval when they start to slowly increase.
648 Around 11.7 ka at 0.53 m the amplification is accelerated reaching a maximum around 8.4 ± 0.6
649 ka at 0.24 m and decreasing afterwards. The transition from loess to soil identified in the field

650 occurs at around 1 m at 14 ka (**Figure S12**), approximately coinciding with the initial rise in
651 magnetic susceptibility

652 To summarize, we identified a gradual and smooth increase in the magnetic susceptibility values
653 over the loess-soil transition in seven sites (PRI, MV, RS, MVS, SM, CX and KUM) spread
654 across the mid-latitude loess belts on three continents. The OSL chronologies indicate
655 continuous dust accumulation and coupled with the magnetic susceptibility variation provide
656 evidence for accretional Holocene soil formation in these sites. In two sites from SE Europe and
657 Chinese Loess Plateau the variation in magnetic susceptibility is sharp (ROX, BCY) and in one
658 of them (ROX), a significant OSL age hiatus is detected at the same depth. However, the
659 luminescence ages in the soil horizons indicate dust accumulation during the Holocene.

660 **6. Modeled mean accumulation rates**

661 The factors that control dust deposition and settling include atmospheric turbulence, the
662 characteristics of the particles transported by wind which are controlled by the potential source
663 areas, the nature of the surface where the dust settles more specifically the topography and
664 vegetation cover and the precipitation rate (Újvári et al., 2016). Based on the evidence that
665 mixing has had little effect on the accuracy of the luminescence ages in the soils and our
666 interpretation that these are accretional soils, dust accumulation rates are modeled in the soils as
667 well as in the underlying loess.

668 At most of the sites studied, accumulation rates are higher in loess, below the increase in
669 magnetic susceptibility, and are lower in the soils, but there are several exceptions (**Figure 11**).
670 That is, the calculated accumulation rates are consistent with the hypothesis that slow
671 sedimentation played a role in enhancing the effectiveness of Holocene pedogenesis in some, but

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Figures 11 A-I. Modeled accumulation rates and frequency dependent magnetic susceptibility signals plotted against the depth. Note that the low frequency magnetic susceptibility signal is represented for Caoxian and Baicaoyuan sites. 1 sigma uncertainties of the sedimentation rates are given with dotted lines. The time intervals covering 11.7 ka and 17.5 ka are hachured with light and dark colour, respectively.

685 not all, cases. In two cases, Ramnicu Sarat and Caoxian, accumulation rates also increase again
686 toward the top of the section. At Caoxian, the increase is associated with lighter colors possibly
687 consistent with increased dust accumulation and weaker pedogenesis. At both these sites,
688 however, the apparent increase in accumulation should be treated with caution as it is based on
689 only two ages in each case at depths where thorough bioturbation is most likely.

690 *Southeastern European belt sites*

691 At Kurortne accumulation rates are similar in Last Glacial Maximum loess and soil units, with
692 no change across the boundary from a dark AB horizons to much less pedogenically altered loess
693 below. Low values of accumulation rates after 17 ka of $3.3 \pm 0.2 \text{ cm ka}^{-1}$ were obtained by
694 modelling luminescence ages. At Roxolany the sediments above the depth where the age gap is
695 identified, after $8.6 \pm 0.7 \text{ ka}$, accumulated at a mean rate of 7 cm ka^{-1} (**Figure 11B**) which is
696 comparable to accumulation rates in the other SE European sites that display a smooth increase
697 in χ_{fd} values. The very low apparent accumulation rate at the base of the soil in this LPS (**Figure**
698 **3**) results from the age jump there at about the same depth as the abrupt increase in magnetic
699 susceptibility, both most plausibly explained by an erosional discontinuity rather than a climatic
700 event. In the loess below the discontinuity mean accumulation rates are higher than in the soil, 17
701 cm ka^{-1} and 7 cm ka^{-1} , respectively.

702 At Mircea Voda, around 17 ka the luminescence ages indicate a decrease in the mean
703 accumulation rate from 20 cm ka^{-1} to 4 cm ka^{-1} near the base of the soil profile (**Figures 4 and**
704 **11C**). The mean accumulation rates after 17 ka vary from 4-9 cm ka^{-1} . The magnetic
705 susceptibility increase at this site begins prior to the change in accumulation rate but most of the
706 increase occurs under conditions of slow accumulation. At Ramnicu Sarat, minimum mean

707 accumulation rates after 11.7 ka reach 6 cm ka⁻¹ (**Figure 11D**), similar to those in soils at most
708 other sites. A large portion of the increase in magnetic susceptibility is associated with these
709 relatively low rates (**Figure 5**). A higher accumulation rate is calculated for the three uppermost
710 samples within the soil, accompanied by some decrease in magnetic susceptibility as noted
711 above. Due to strong inversions for ages older than 12 ka we were unable to calculate reliable
712 accumulation rates. At Mošorin Veliki Surduk, the mean accumulation rates vary from 25 cm ka⁻¹
713 ¹ before 14 ka to a minimum of 2 cm ka⁻¹ after 11.7 ka. Most increase in magnetic susceptibility
714 occurs after the shift to slower accumulation (**Figure 11**), which occurs near the base of the soil
715 (**Figure 6**). Finally, at Smederevo, the mean accumulation rate is similar for loess and soil units
716 varying from 5 to 7 cm ka⁻¹, and the increase in magnetic susceptibility is not associated with
717 slower accumulation (**Figure 11**).

718 *Chinese Loess Plateau and Great Plains Sites*

719 At all three of these LPS, accumulation rates decreased substantially from underlying loess into
720 the soils. At Caoxian the modeled accumulation rates decrease from 30 cm ka⁻¹ before 14 ka to a
721 minimum of 9 cm ka⁻¹ after 11.7 ka, with the change occurring in transitional horizons between
722 unweathered loess and more pedogenically altered horizons (**Figures 8 and 11**). The calculated
723 sediment rate increases to higher values again in the late Holocene at Caoxian. At Baicaoyuan,
724 mean accumulation rates of around 15 cm ka⁻¹ were determined during and prior to 11.7 ka after
725 which they decrease to a minimum of 5 cm ka⁻¹ for the Holocene soil (**Figure 11 H**); this
726 reduction occurs well above the base of the soil (**Figure 9**). These are similar to the values
727 obtained at the Caoxian site as well as the European sites. At Kuma reduction in the mean
728 accumulation rate from 154 cm ka⁻¹ to 6 cm ka⁻¹ occurs around 14 ka, as well (**Figure 11 I**).

729 While the accumulation rate in the loess below the soil at Kuma is higher compared to other
730 sites, this is expected for the central Great Plains (**Roberts et al., 2003**).

731 At all three of these sites both the stratigraphy and the OSL chronology demonstrated a
732 continuous record of dust deposition, though at varying rates, that competed with pedogenesis
733 from the Late Pleistocene through the Holocene. The rapid jump in the magnetic susceptibility
734 signal around 11.7 ka at Baicaoyuan is distinctive, but at all three sites, much of the total increase
735 in magnetic susceptibility occurred following the decline of the accumulation to lower levels
736 characteristic of much of the Holocene.

737 **7. Discussion**

738 *7.1 Timing of the initiation and acceleration of the magnetic susceptibility enhancement in loess* 739 *deposits*

740 In the majority of the sites investigated in this study the onset of magnetic susceptibility
741 enhancement was dated prior to 11.7 ka, around 14-17.5 ka (Kurortne, Roxolany, Ramnicu Sarat,
742 Mošorin in the SE European loess belt, Caoxian in Chinese Loess Plateau and Kuma from
743 Central Great Plains, USA; **Figures 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 10**) or even earlier (Mircea Voda and
744 Smederevo from the SE European loess belt; **Figures 4, 7**). At one site the magnetic
745 susceptibility signal starts to increase sharply around 11.7 ka (Baicaoyuan from Chinese Loess
746 Plateau; **Figure 9**).

747 The rate of increase in magnetic susceptibility record accelerates around 11.7 ka at some but not
748 all of these sites, (Kurortne, Mircea Voda and Mošorin from SE European loess belt, Caoxian
749 from western Chinese Loess Plateau and Kuma from Central Great Plain, USA; **Figures 2, 4, 6,**
750 **8, 10**).

751 Here we assume that the start of the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition produces the onset
752 of magnetic susceptibility signal amplification in the investigated loess deposits. Based on the
753 luminescence ages, the transition occurs around 14-17.5 ka and it precedes the 11.7 ka date of
754 the chronostratigraphic Pleistocene-Holocene boundary defined in ice-cores records (**Rasmussen**
755 **et al., 2014**).

756 *Comparison with absolute ages reported for Chinese Loess Plateau*

757 In the Yuanbao loess section, located in the western CLP, based on quartz luminescence ages,
758 **Lai and Wintle (2006)** date the onset and acceleration of magnetic susceptibility enhancement
759 to ~15 ka and ~9.8 ka, respectively. They place the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition
760 based on the changes in the sensitivity of the luminescence signals in quartz and report an age of
761 ~ 13 ka.

762 At the Beiguoyuan, Xifeng, Xunyi, and Shiguanzhai loess sections, distributed across the CLP
763 from north to south, it is more difficult to accurately date the initial increase in magnetic
764 susceptibility, because the start of this increase falls within intervals in which luminescence ages
765 are scattered with inversions and/or display gaps interpreted as hiatuses (**Lu et al., 2006; Stevens**
766 **et al., 2006; 2007; 2008**). These intervals cover various times between 20 ka and < 10 ka,
767 differing between sites. Similarly, in the central CLP, at Luochuan site, at the depth interval
768 where the onset of magnetic susceptibility enhancement occurs, high-resolution (10 cm)
769 luminescence ages suddenly jump to ~17 ka, yielding a ~6 ka age gap across 50 cm (**Lu et al.,**
770 **2013**).

771 The timing and smoothness of magnetic susceptibility increase at Caoxian are similar to the
772 Yuanbao site and the ~14 ka date reported there. A close resemblance in the magnetic

773 susceptibility signal intensity of the glacial loess ($\sim 30 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$) and soil ($60\text{-}70 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$)
774 can be seen between the Caoxian site (western CLP) and Huanxian site (central-north CLP)
775 (**Dong et al., 2015**) that display much lower values compared to Yuanbao site, $50 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$ and
776 $170 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$ for loess and soil, respectively.

777 The second site from the western CLP reported in this study, Baicaoyuan, is similar to Yuanbao
778 site only in terms of magnetic susceptibility signal intensities of $50 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$ and $170 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$
779 for loess and soil, respectively. The increase in magnetic susceptibility is much more abrupt at
780 Baicaoyuan and also displays a short-term fluctuation early in the increase. A similar short-term
781 fluctuation is evident at the Luochuan site, but occurs later, in the early Holocene (**Lu et al.,**
782 **2013**).

783 **Dong et al. (2015)** noted relatively abrupt shifts in the magnetic susceptibility record with ages
784 decreasing from southeast to northwest across the plateau ($\sim 11 \text{ ka}$ to $\sim 7 \text{ ka}$). They attribute the
785 time transgressive nature of this shift to the gradual strengthening of the Asian Summer
786 Monsoon (ASM) and the consequent changes in precipitation to which the magnetic
787 susceptibility signal is sensitive. In this study, the luminescence ages on the two sites from west
788 CLP investigated, reveal a relatively small inverse gradient with the ages increasing from ~ 11.7
789 ka ($\pm 1 \text{ ka}$) in Baicaoyuan (farther south) to $\sim 14 \text{ ka}$ ($\pm 1 \text{ ka}$) in Caoxian (farther north) for the
790 onset of magnetic susceptibility increase.

791 This comparison with results of previous research demonstrates significant remaining issues in
792 establishing the timing of the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition as recorded by magnetic
793 susceptibility in the CLP. At both Yuanbao (**Lai and Wintle, 2006**) and the Caoxian LPS
794 sampled for this study, luminescence dating indicates relatively continuous records through the

795 interval 10-15 ka and magnetic susceptibility increases gradually with the increase beginning at
796 15-13 ka. At several other previously studied sites, the luminescence chronology indicates
797 hiatuses covering the interval 10-15 ka; these records do not confirm initiation of the increase in
798 magnetic susceptibility at 15-13 ka but apparently do not rule it out (e.g. **Stevens et al., 2008,**
799 **Fig. 19-20 therein**). The Baicaoyuan LPS also has a luminescence chronology indicating
800 continuous sedimentation, but displays a more abrupt and later initial increase of magnetic
801 susceptibility than at Caoxian and Yuanbao. This contrast likely reflects some local variation in
802 Pleistocene-Holocene environmental change, but cannot be further explained without data from
803 additional sites with continuous records through the key time interval.

804 *Comparison with previous research in the south-eastern European loess belt*

805 To our knowledge, the literature lacks high resolution OSL studies on the Pleistocene-Holocene
806 climatic transition recorded in the European loess sites. Generally, there is a good agreement
807 between our results and the ones previously reported. Based on one quartz OSL age the magnetic
808 susceptibility starts to increase before 13 ± 1 ka in Orlovat site (**Marković et al., 2014; Timar-**
809 **Gabor et al., 2015**) and around 13 ± 1 ka in Crvenka site, Vojvodina region, Middle Danube
810 Basin (**Stevens et al., 2011; Marković et al., 2018**). However, at Surduk, in the same region, a
811 very young ^{14}C age of 7.3 ± 0.38 cal ka BP (**Hatté et al., 2013**) is reported for the onset of
812 magnetic susceptibility enhancement. A quartz OSL age of 11 ± 1 ka is reported above the area
813 of magnetic susceptibility enhancement in Lunca (**Constantin et al. 2015**) and Urluia
814 (**Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014**) sites in the Lower Danube Basin. Regarding the Black Sea
815 loess region in Ukraine, magnetic susceptibility investigations have been carried out by
816 **Nawrocki et al. (1999)** and **Bakhmutov et al. (2017)**, among others, but this area lacks reliable
817 numerical datings.

818 *Comparison with previous research in the Central Great Plains*

819 The Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition is expressed in Central Great Plains, and more
820 specifically in loess of Nebraska and Kansas, from a stratigraphical point of view, by the
821 transition from Peoria loess deposited during the last glacial (late Wisconsin) period ca 28 ka to
822 about 14-13 ka to a dark, organic rich buried soil, the Brady Soil.(e.g. **Johnson and Willey,**
823 **2000; Mason et al., 2003; Roberts et al., 2003; Mason et al., 2008; Schatzl et al., 2018;**
824 **Tecsa et al., 2020b**). After the formation of the Brady soil, accelerated dust deposition during
825 Holocene formed Bignell loess (e.g. **Mason et al., 2003; Miao et al., 2007; Tecsa et al., 2020b**).
826 Across large areas of the central Great Plains that are farther from Holocene loess sources, the
827 Brady Soil is at < 1 m depth and has often been transformed into a horizon of the modern soil
828 (**Jacobs and Mason, 2007**). The Brady Soil is not preserved at all on most slopes or narrow
829 ridge tops.

830 The Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition in LPS containing the Brady Soil has been
831 investigated using OSL and radiocarbon dating (**Mason et al., 2003; Roberts et al., 2003; Miao**
832 **et al., 2007; Mason et al., 2008; Tecsa et al., 2020b**) and analysis of variations in stable carbon
833 isotope ratios ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) in organic matter and carbonates, particle size, and phytoliths (**Johnson and**
834 **Willey, 2000;Feggestad et al., 2004; Miao et al., 2007; Woodburn et al., 2017; Tecsa et al.,**
835 **2020b**). Studies of rock magnetic properties are less common, and have revealed that in some
836 LPS of this region, the Brady Soil or other paleosols is not represented by a well-defined peak of
837 magnetic susceptibility (**Johnson and Willey, 2000;Miao et al., 2007; Tecsa et al., 2020b**).
838 However, the increase in magnetic susceptibility to a peak in the Brady Soil is well-defined at
839 the Kuma LPS reported here and at some sites studied by **Johnson and Willey (2000)**.

840

841 **Roberts et al. (2003)** first reported quartz OSL dating of the uppermost Peoria Loess just below
842 the Brady Soil at the Bignell Hill LPS. **Mason et al. (2008)** reported quartz OSL and radiocarbon
843 ages and summarized previously reported dating, from the upper Peoria Loess through the Brady
844 Soil in six LPS of western Nebraska, including paired OSL and radiocarbon ages at 10 cm
845 spacing through the Brady Soil at the Old Wauneta Road cut. Based on that compilation, the
846 uppermost Peoria Loess was deposited rapidly at 14-15 ka. OSL ages just below the lower A
847 horizon of the Brady Soil range from 12.6 to 15.8 ka, with most between 13 and 15 ka, while
848 OSL ages just above the Brady Soil are mostly between 9 and 10 ka. Radiocarbon ages are
849 largely consistent with the OSL dating, including the paired ages at the Old Wauneta Roadcut.
850 **Tecsa et al. (2020b)** report OSL ages based on multiple grain sizes of quartz at the Enders LPS,
851 dating the base of the Brady Soil to 13.1 ± 0.8 ka and the top of it to 9.5 ± 0.6 ka.

852
853 Importantly, at the Enders LPS, the shift toward finer particle size that characterizes the Brady
854 Soil begins below the age of 13.1 ka assigned to the field identified base of the soil and about 20
855 cm above an age of 14.0 ± 0.9 ka (**Tecsa et al., 2020b**). The particle size record from the Enders
856 LPS is therefore closely consistent with the initiation of magnetic susceptibility enhancement at
857 Kuma site, dated to ~ 14 ka, although higher in the Brady Soil, particle size variation is more
858 complex than the steady increase of magnetic enhancement to an early Holocene peak at Kuma.
859 At Enders a major shift in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of carbonates, tentatively interpreted as indicating growing
860 abundance of C_4 grasses with warming temperature (**Tecsa et al., 2020b**), based on correlation
861 with carbon isotopic records from organic matter at nearby sites (**Feggestad et al., 2004; Miao**
862 **et al., 2007**) begins at a similar depth as the shift to finer particle size. All of these proxies are

863 likely to record specific aspects of Pleistocene-Holocene environmental change, with different
864 temporal patterns corresponding to the specific factors they respond to.

865
866 **Johnson and Willey (2000)** present the magnetic susceptibility record for Peoria loess-Brady
867 soil-Bignell loess at three sites in Kansas: DB, Biesel-Steinle and Mills, in χ_{lf} enhancement is
868 clearly evident in the Brady Soil while while the χ_{fd} (%) signal is only sensitive to Brady Soil
869 pedogenesis at the DB site. Only one or two radiocarbon ages from organic matter are available
870 at each of these sites (**Johnson and Willey, 2000**), and those from DB and Mills sites are
871 anomalously young relative to other dating of the Brady Soil across the region. A calibrated age
872 of 13.3 ka near the start of the increase in magnetic susceptibility at Beisel-Steinle is consistent
873 with regional chronology and also not much younger than the age of ~14 ka at this point in the
874 Kuma LPS.

875
876 Based on these observations we deduce that the stratigraphic patterns of magnetic susceptibility
877 records across the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition are not synchronous in the sites
878 investigated from the SE European Loess Belt, Chinese Loess Plateau and Central Great Plains,
879 US.

880 *7.2 Accretional soil formation in loess regions and implications for interpreting loess records*

881 Our interpretation of luminescence dating within soils at the study sites as indicating ongoing
882 Late Pleistocene to Holocene dust accumulation clearly implies accretional pedogenesis in some
883 form. In the Holocene environments of these LPS, dust accumulating at rates of $< 10 \text{ cm ka}^{-1}$
884 would have been altered by organic matter accumulation, soil structure formation, and other
885 pedogenetic processes quickly enough to allow the soil grow upward over time.

886 In this section we consider the process of accretional pedogenesis in these LPS in more detail,
887 and its implications for interpretation of the paleoclimatic record they preserve. As discussed in
888 previous research (e.g. **McDonald and Busacca, 1990; Almond and Tonkin, 1999; Kemp,**
889 **2001; Mason and Jacobs, 2007**), each new increment of dust is added at the surface where a
890 specific set of pedogenetic processes are most effective, then is progressively buried and in effect
891 moved into the shallow subsurface. It can be altered there by the conditions and processes that
892 produce soil B horizons but eventually, through ongoing burial it can reach a point where it is no
893 longer significantly affected by pedogenesis. In other words, dust added at the surface can be
894 incorporated into an upbuilding A horizon as it gains organic matter, while at the same time, an
895 earlier-formed part of the A horizon may be losing organic matter and acquiring a color and
896 structure more characteristic of B horizons. **Mason and Jacobs (2007)** describe this process for
897 many sites the central Great Plains, mostly farther east and in more humid environments than the
898 Kuma LPS.

899 Importantly though, the specific transformations that take place must be related to the
900 environmental conditions and rate of dust accumulation. Rapid accumulation in a cold, dry
901 environment, often inferred for Late Pleistocene loess, allows only minor alteration in the near-
902 surface (e.g. root traces, subtle biogenic and/or cryogenic structures visible in thin sections, etc.)
903 before deep burial (**Kemp et al., 1995; Kemp, 2001**). Slower accumulation in a climate that is
904 warmer with more effective moisture but still semiarid to subhumid could allow more
905 accumulation of organic matter and strong granular structure in the near-surface zone, which is
906 then mostly preserved as it moves into the dry subsoil, leading to the appearance of over
907 thickened A horizons. In more humid climates with slow accumulation, organic matter could be
908 rapidly lost in the subsoil, leading to transformation of A horizons into apparent B horizons

909 (alternative forms of A to B transformation in more arid environments are also described by
910 **McDonald and Busacca, 1990**).

911 This conceptual model can be applied to the studied LPS as follows: In the earliest stages of the
912 Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition at these sites, the processes that produce magnetic
913 enhancement in near-surface horizons gradually became more effective as dust continued to
914 accumulate. Studies of non-accretional soils typically find the magnitude and depth of magnetic
915 enhancement in nonaccretional soils vary with climate, parent material, and soil age; however, in
916 latest Pleistocene to Holocene nonaccretional soils in semiarid climates the magnetic
917 enhancement appears to be the greatest near the surface and largely confined to the uppermost
918 few tens of cm, except in soils much older than those at our study sites (**Singer and Fine, 1989**;
919 **Quinton et al., 2011**). Those observations support our interpretation of the initial increase in
920 magnetic susceptibility as having formed soon after deposition of the loess at that depth, and
921 preserved by ongoing dust accumulation, rather than through top down pedogenesis
922 contemporaneous with development of the overlying better-developed horizons. Further research
923 is needed to determine how much other evidence of weak pedogenesis at the depth of the initial
924 magnetic susceptibility increase or just above it can be attributed to the earliest stages of the
925 climatic transition and possibly used to provide additional paleoenvironmental interpretations.

926 As the climatic transition continued and the accumulation rate decreased at many of the study
927 sites, magnetic enhancement and the effects of other pedogenetic processes became more
928 pronounced. In LPS of the Chinese Loess Plateau and the Great Plains, and at some of the
929 Southeastern European sites, this process continued into the Holocene, resulting in a relatively
930 thick sequence of primarily A and AB horizons with varying degrees of structural development
931 and organic matter accumulation. Pedogenetic carbonate accumulation likely formed below the

932 currently active surface A horizon, overprinting deeper horizons formed earlier in the accretional
933 process (supported by isotopic data from carbonates and organic matter at loess sections near
934 Kuma, **Tecsa et al., 2020b**). It is possible that some deeper horizons originated as A horizons but
935 now resemble B horizons because of post-burial loss of organic matter and structural changes,
936 especially in the Southeastern European LPS. At sites in the Chinese Loess Plateau and Great
937 Plains, more weakly developed, lighter-colored upper horizons reflect change to a drier climate
938 later in the Holocene.

939 If this conceptual model is accurate and applies more generally to LPS spanning the Pleistocene-
940 Holocene transition, then it is valid to interpret vertical profiles of not only magnetic parameters,
941 but also isotopic composition of organic matter (e.g. **Miao et al., 2007**) as essentially time series
942 produced by steady upbuilding of the land surface by dust deposition. The same could be true of
943 carbonate isotopic composition (e.g. **Tecsa et al., 2020b**) and other pedogenetic properties and
944 features, though more research is needed to assess the depth range over which they form in these
945 accretional soils. Some “smearing” of these records must be acknowledged, because magnetic
946 enhancement and organic matter addition both occur over a zone of some thickness below the
947 ground surface, and because of bio- or cryoturbation likely always have at least minor effects
948 over some depth scale. However, in a semiarid steppe environment where deeper horizons are
949 rarely wetted, these records are probably locked in after burial to sufficient depth.

950 **8. Conclusions**

951 In this study we have measured at very high-resolution the magnetic susceptibility record across
952 the transition from the last glacial loess to the Holocene soil in nine sites from the Chinese Loess
953 Plateau, southeastern European loess-belt and central Great Plains, Nebraska, USA. In all sites

954 but two (Baicaoyuan and Roxolany) the magnetic susceptibility signal increases gradually. We
955 have placed the onset of the magnetic susceptibility enhancement at the depth where the χ_{fd}
956 values increase significantly and continuously compared to those values that characterize the late
957 glacial loess (or where available LGM loess) following the approach of **Stern and Lisiecki**
958 **(2014)** for the oxygen isotope chronology in marine sediments.

959 Using high-resolution luminescence dating on multiple grain-size fractions of quartz we dated
960 the onset of magnetic susceptibility enhancement and consequently the onset of Pleistocene-
961 Holocene climatic transition recorded in Chinese Loess Plateau, southeastern European loess belt
962 and central Great Plain loess deposits prior to 11.7 ka, around 14-17.5 ka. Thus, we conclude
963 that, the onset of the Pleistocene-Holocene climatic transition recorded in loess deposits by the
964 magnetic susceptibility signal is not synchronous among all of the investigated sites from
965 Chinese Loess Plateau, southeastern European belt and central Great Plains, Nebraska, USA. The
966 timing of this transition generally agrees, however, with the ~ 17.5 ka date for Termination 1 in
967 oxygen isotopes in marine sediments reported by **Stern and Lisiecki (2014)** and is earlier than
968 the Pleistocene-Holocene chronostratigraphic boundary set at 11.7 ka.

969 The detailed luminescence chronology points to a continuous dust accumulation during the
970 Pleistocene-Holocene transition as well as into the Holocene at the investigated sites. Coupled
971 with other evidence it indicates that dust sedimentation and pedogenesis act simultaneously and
972 result in the formation of accretional Holocene soils at the sites investigated, with important
973 implications for the interpretation of magnetic susceptibility and other paleoclimatic proxies.
974 While accretional pedogenesis has often been implicitly or explicitly assumed in paleoclimatic
975 interpretation of loess-paleosol sequences, especially in the Chinese Loess Plateau, our
976 luminescence data add direct evidence for ongoing sedimentation as soils formed. The high

977 resolution luminescence ages allowed modeling of accumulation rates for the Holocene soil that
978 are similar for European, Chinese and US loess sites investigated here and vary between 2 cm ka⁻¹
979 ¹ to 9 cm ka⁻¹.

980 Our results highlight the need of combining absolute dating with high-resolution paleoclimatic
981 proxies (e.g. magnetic susceptibility) to accurately estimate the timing of the Pleistocene-
982 Holocene climatic transition from these complex records produced by dust accumulation and
983 accretional pedogenesis. Presented results indicate diverse environmental dynamics recorded in
984 the different North Hemisphere loess regions during the major global climatic shift such as the
985 transition from the last glacial to the Holocene. Understanding of these asynchronous responses
986 of the terrestrial ecosystem to the past global climate changes is important for adequate
987 interpretations of current and prediction of future interactions between climatic and
988 environmental evolution.

989 **Authors contribution**

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1002 measurements **Alida Timar-Gabor:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Sampling,
1003 Methodology, Luminescence investigations, Writing the original draft, Supervision.

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Figure S1. Map of loess distribution in southeastern Europe modified after **Haase et al. (2007)**. The six loess sites investigated in this study are located in Ukraine, Romania and Serbia.

Figure S2. Kurortne site, Ukraine, SE Europe. Left: the long profile presented by **(Tecsá et al., 2020a)** covering the Last Interglacial-Glacial cycle. Right: close-up of the Pleistocene-Holocene transition investigated in this study. The weighted OSL ages are indicated for each sampling point.

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Figure S3. Roxolany site, Ukraine, SE Europe. Photo adapted from **Constantin et al. (2019)**. The weighted average OSL age corresponding to each sampling point are indicated.

Figure S4. Mircea-Voda site, Romania. Photo adapted from **Groza et al. (2020)**. The weighted average OSL age corresponding to each sampling point are indicated.

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Figure S5. Ramnicu Sarat profile, Romania (Constantin et al., 2019). The OSL samples and 63-90 μm quartz ages are indicated. The sample codes comprise the depth (cm) from which each sample has been collected.

Figure S6. Mošorin Veliki Surduk profile, Serbia (Constantin et al., 2019). The OSL sampling points and weighted average of the fine and coarse quartz ages for each sample are indicated.

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Figure S7. Smederevo profile, Serbia. The OSL sampling points and 63-90 μm quartz ages are indicated. The sample codes comprise the depth (cm) from which each sample has been collected.

Figure S8. Map of the Chinese Loess Plateau and its location in along the Yellow River in China (taken from **Zhao et al., 2013**). The studied sites Caoxian and Baicaoyuan are located in the western part and are represented with white stars.

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Figure S9. Caoxian profile, Chinese Loess Plateau. The OSL sampling points and 63-90 μm quartz ages are indicated.

Figure S10. Baicaoyuan profile, Chinese Loess Plateau. The OSL sampling points and weighted average of the fine and coarse quartz ages for each sample are indicated.

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Figure S11 Location of Kuma site (Nebraska). To the left, location within the Great Plains loess belt (adapted from **Muhs, 2013**). To the right, local setting of the Kuma site and the previously studied Enders (E, **Tecsa et al., 2020b**) and Wauneta (W, **Miao et al., 2007**) sections, on plateaus underlain by thick loess, downwind (southeast) from landscapes with thin loess and aeolian sand (light shade).

Figure S12. Kuma profile, Nebraska. The weighted average OSL age corresponding to each sampling point are indicated.

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Figure S13. Representative dose-response curves measured on one aliquot of different grain-sizes of quartz extracted from selected samples from Baicaoyuan, Caoxian and Kuma sites. The comparison between the rates of decay of the natural and regenerative luminescence signals of each sample and calibration quartz is shown in the insets.

Figure S14. The variation of the measured equivalent dose with the temperature of heating treatment applied before natural and regenerative signal readout. The aliquots were heated to 180 °C before the readout of the luminescence signal induced by the test dose. The sample code and grain-size fraction are indicated. ROX (Roxolany, Ukraine), RS (Ramnicu Sarat, Romania), MVS (Mosorin, Serbia) reported in Constantin et al. (2019), BCY (Baicaoyuan, Chinese Loess Plateau), KUM (Kuma, Nebraska, USA).

Figure S15. Summary of dose recovery test ratio results on quartz of different grain-sizes extracted samples from the following sites: Baicaoyuan (Bcy) from China, Kuma (Kum)

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from Nebraska, US, Roxolany (Rox; **Constantin et al., 2019**) and Kurortne (Pri; **Tecsa et al., 2020**) from Ukraine, Ramnicu Sarat (RS; **Constantin et al., 2019**) from Romania and Mošorin Veliki Surduk (MVS; **Constantin et al., 2019**) from Serbia. Each data point represents the average of five measurements. The given dose approximated the equivalent dose for. The solid line indicates the ideal 1:1 dose recovery ratio while the dash lines bracket a 10% variation from unity.

Sample BCY 1.2 (transition Glacial loess- Holocene soil). To the left the results on 63-90 μ m quartz and to the right the 4-11 μ m quartz.

KUM 1.4 63-90 μ m (Holocene soil)

KUM 1.7 63-90 μ m (transition Glacial loess- Holocene soil)

Figure S16. Radial plots showing the equivalent dose distribution obtained on 63-90 μm and 4-11 μm quartz samples collected around the transition from Last Glacial loess to Holocene in Baicaoyuan site (Chinese Loess Plateau) and 63-90 μm quartz collected around the transition from Last Glacial loess to Holocene as well as the Holocene soil in Kuma site, Nebraska. n represents the number of aliquots analysed. The plots were generated in the R luminescence package using the ‘plot_RadialPlot’-function (Dietze et al., 2016).

Table S10. Relative standard deviation, RSD, (%) and equivalent dose overdispersion, OD, (%) calculated for 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm quartz extracted soil and loess samples from the following sites Kurortne (Ukraine), Mircea-Voda (Romania), Caoxian and Baicaoyuan (China) and Kuma (Nebraska).

Unit	Sample code	Grain-size (μm)	De \pm st.err.	Number of aliquots	RSD (%)	OD (%)
Holocene soil	PRI 1.2	63-90	15 \pm 1	10	29	26
		90-125	14 \pm 1	12	27	25
Loess-soil transition	PRI 1.6	63-90	38 \pm 2	10	13	12
		90-125	35 \pm 3	12	26	23
Loess	PRI 1.8	63-90	89 \pm 4	10	14	13
		90-125	63 \pm 4	12	22	22
Holocene soil	2MV60	63-90	22 \pm 2	21	32	30
	2MV80	63-90	36 \pm 3	18	31	31
Loess-soil transition	2MV2.2	63-90	54 \pm 3	23	21	21
Loess	2MV2.6	63-90	87 \pm 4	20	23	22
Holocene soil	CX1.3	63-90	13.4 \pm 0.3	13	9	6
Loess-soil transition	CX2.5	63-90	30 \pm 2	15	23	14
Loess	CX2.2	63-90	41 \pm 2	14	16	15
Holocene soil	BCY 1.8	63-90	23 \pm 1	10	12	12
Loess-soil transition	BCY 1.3	63-90	39 \pm 1	13	13	12
	BCY 1.2	63-90	42 \pm 1	51	14	14

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Loess	BCY 1.0	63-90	48±2	11	11	9
Holocene soil	KUM 1.4	63-90	52 ± 1	22	7	6
Loess-soil transition	KUM 1.7	63-90	54 ± 1	19	10	9

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Table S1. Kurortne, Ukraine. Summary of the luminescence and dosimetry data. Weighted OSL ages are calculated according to **Aitken (1985)**. The uncertainties associated with the luminescence and dosimetry data are random; the uncertainties mentioned with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. All uncertainties represent 1σ . Specific activities were measured on Well detector and the ages were determined considering the “as found” water content, with a relative error of 25%; n denotes the number of accepted aliquots; beta attenuation and etching factor used for 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm fractions are 0.94 ± 0.050 and 0.92 ± 0.050 , respectively; adopted alpha efficiency factor was 0.04 ± 0.02 . The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the alpha, beta and gamma radiations as well as the contribution from the cosmic radiation.

Sample code	Depth (cm)	Grain size (μm)	Water content (%)	De (Gy)	U-Ra (Bq/kg)	Th (Bq/kg)	K (Bq/kg)	Total random error (%)	Total Systematic error (%)	Total dose rate (Gy/ka)	Age (ka)	Weighted ages (ka)
PRI 1.1	15	4-11	4.4	3.5 ± 0.1 (n=11)	42.8 ± 1.3	40.6 ± 1.2	508 ± 15	3.2	7.9	4.00 ± 0.06	0.9 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.01
		63-90		1.1 ± 0.1 (n=10)				9.2	5.5	3.36 ± 0.05	0.3 ± 0.0	
		90-125		0.8 ± 0.1 (n=10)				12.6	5.4	3.32 ± 0.05	0.2 ± 0.0	
PRI 1.2	30	4-11	6.2	15.4 ± 0.1 (n=11)	41.3 ± 1.5	39.4 ± 1.5	507 ± 14	1.8	7.9	3.83 ± 0.06	4.0 ± 0.3	4.2 ± 0.3
		63-90		14.7 ± 1.4 (n=10)				9.7	5.6	3.22 ± 0.05	4.6 ± 0.5	
		90-125		13.8 ± 1.1 (n=12)				8.1	5.6	3.18 ± 0.05	4.3 ± 0.4	
PRI 1.3	43	4-11	2.8	24.0 ± 0.7 (n=11)	38.6 ± 0.1	41.6 ± 1.1	485 ± 16	3.3	7.9	3.87 ± 0.06	6.2 ± 0.5	6.1 ± 0.4
		63-90		24.1 ± 2.3 (n=10)				9.7	5.4	3.24 ± 0.05	7.4 ± 0.8	
		90-125		17.2 ± 1.4 (n=12)				8.3	5.4	3.20 ± 0.05	5.4 ± 0.5	
PRI 1.4	53	4-11	2.2	30.4 ± 0.4 (n=10)	37.0 ± 0.9	33.4 ± 0.8	447 ± 13	2.0	7.8	3.52 ± 0.05	8.6 ± 0.7	9.1 ± 0.6
		63-90		28.7 ± 2.0 (n=10)				7.1	5.4	2.96 ± 0.05	9.7 ± 0.9	
		90-125		26.7 ± 1.4 (n=12)				5.5	5.4	2.92 ± 0.05	9.1 ± 0.7	
PRI 1.5	58	4-11	6.7	32.6 ± 0.7 (n=11)	37.3 ± 0.3	35.2 ± 0.3	453 ± 13	2.5	8.0	3.41 ± 0.04	9.6 ± 0.8	9.3 ± 0.6
		63-90		26.6 ± 1.5 (n=11)				5.8	5.6	2.87 ± 0.04	9.3 ± 0.8	
		90-125		26.2 ± 1.0 (n=12)				4.1	5.6	2.83 ± 0.04	9.2 ± 0.6	
PRI 1.6	68	4-11	6.5	39.5 ± 0.4 (n=12)	38.2 ± 1.4	35.5 ± 1.3	496 ± 16	2.1	7.8	3.58 ± 0.07	11.0 ± 0.9	11.7 ± 0.8
		63-90		37.9 ± 1.6 (n=10)				4.6	5.7	3.02 ± 0.06	12.5 ± 0.9	
		90-125		34.8 ± 2.6 (n=12)				7.7	5.6	2.99 ± 0.06	11.7 ± 1.1	
PRI 1.7	85	4-11	8.5	42.9 ± 0.5 (n=10)	36.1 ± 1.0	33.4 ± 1.3	448 ± 12	2.0	8.1	3.25 ± 0.05	13.2 ± 1.1	13.8 ± 1.0
		63-90		41.8 ± 2.6 (n=11)				6.4	5.8	2.74 ± 0.04	15.3 ± 1.3	

		90-125		36.1 ± 2.5 (n=10)				7.1	5.8	2.70 ± 0.04	13.4 ± 1.2	
PRI 1.8	115	4-11	7.7	89.4 ± 1.1 (n=10)	38.0 ± 1.1	39.4 ± 0.5	447 ± 13	1.8	8.3	3.45 ± 0.05	25.9 ± 2.2	25.8 ± 1.7
		63-90		88.7 ± 4.0 (n=10)				4.7	5.7	2.88 ± 0.04	30.8 ± 2.3	
		90-125		62.8 ± 4.1 (n=12)				6.7	5.7	2.85 ± 0.04	22.0 ± 1.9	
PRI 1.9	150	4-11	4.2	123 ± 1 (n=10)	33.1 ± 1.5	36.5 ± 1.0	458 ± 13	1.9	7.8	3.41 ± 0.06	36.2 ± 2.9	37.7 ± 2.4
		63-90		111 ± 5 (n=10)				4.9	5.5	2.87 ± 0.05	38.7 ± 2.8	
		90-125		108 ± 4 (n=12)				3.8	5.5	2.84 ± 0.05	38.0 ± 2.5	
		63-90		313 ± 15 (n=10)				5.2	6.0	2.55 ± 0.05	123 ± 10	
		90-125		280 ± 11 (n=10)				4.5	6.0	2.52 ± 0.05	111 ± 8	

Table 3. OSL ages calculated assuming different past moisture scenarios.

Sample code	Depth (cm)	Grain size (μm)	ED (Gy)	Age(ka) (As found water content)	Age (ka) (5% water content)	Age (ka) (10% water content)
PRI 1.1	15	4-11	3.5 ± 0.1 (n=11)	0.9 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1
		63-90	1.1 ± 0.1 (n=10)	0.3 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0
		90-125	0.8 ± 0.1 (n=10)	0.2 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0
PRI 1.2	30	4-11	15.4 ± 0.1 (n=11)	4.0 ± 0.3	4.0 ± 0.3	4.2 ± 0.4
		63-90	14.7 ± 1.4 (n=10)	4.6 ± 0.5	4.5 ± 0.5	4.7 ± 0.5
		90-125	13.8 ± 1.1 (n=12)	4.3 ± 0.4	4.3 ± 0.4	4.5 ± 0.5
PRI 1.3	43	4-11	24.0 ± 0.7 (n=11)	6.2 ± 0.5	6.4 ± 0.5	6.7 ± 0.6
		63-90	24.1 ± 2.3 (n=10)	7.4 ± 0.8	7.6 ± 0.8	8.0 ± 0.9
		90-125	17.2 ± 1.4 (n=12)	5.4 ± 0.5	5.5 ± 0.5	5.8 ± 0.6
PRI 1.4	53	4-11	30.4 ± 0.4 (n=10)	8.6 ± 0.7	8.9 ± 0.7	9.4 ± 0.8
		63-90	28.7 ± 2.0 (n=10)	9.7 ± 0.9	10.0 ± 0.9	10.5 ± 1.0
		90-125	26.7 ± 1.4 (n=12)	9.1 ± 0.7	9.4 ± 0.7	9.9 ± 0.8
PRI 1.5	58	4-11	32.6 ± 0.7 (n=11)	9.6 ± 0.8	9.4 ± 0.8	9.9 ± 0.9
		63-90	26.6 ± 1.5 (n=11)	9.3 ± 0.8	9.1 ± 0.7	9.6 ± 0.8
		90-125	26.2 ± 1.0 (n=12)	9.2 ± 0.6	9.1 ± 0.6	9.6 ± 0.7
PRI 1.6	68	4-11	39.5 ± 0.4 (n=12)	11.0 ± 0.9	10.8 ± 0.9	11.4 ± 1.0
		63-90	37.9 ± 1.6 (n=10)	12.5 ± 0.9	12.3 ± 0.9	13.0 ± 1.0
		90-125	34.8 ± 2.6 (n=12)	11.7 ± 1.1	11.5 ± 1.1	12.1 ± 1.2
PRI 1.7	85	4-11	42.9 ± 0.5 (n=10)	13.2 ± 1.1	12.7 ± 1.0	13.4 ± 1.1
		63-90	41.8 ± 2.6 (n=11)	15.3 ± 1.3	14.7 ± 1.2	15.5 ± 1.4
		90-125	36.1 ± 2.5 (n=10)	13.4 ± 1.2	12.9 ± 1.2	13.6 ± 1.3
PRI 1.8	115	4-11	89.4 ± 1.1 (n=10)	25.9 ± 2.2	25.2 ± 2.1	26.6 ± 2.3
		63-90	88.7 ± 4.0 (n=10)	30.8 ± 2.3	29.9 ± 2.2	31.5 ± 2.4
		90-125	62.8 ± 4.1 (n=12)	22.0 ± 1.9	21.4 ± 1.9	22.6 ± 2.0
PRI 1.9	150	4-11	123 ± 1 (n=10)	36.2 ± 2.9	36.5 ± 2.9	38.5 ± 3.2
		63-90	111 ± 5 (n=10)	38.7 ± 2.8	39.0 ± 2.9	41.1 ± 3.2
		90-125	108 ± 4 (n=12)	38.0 ± 2.5	38.3 ± 2.6	40.3 ± 2.9
PRI 1.10	227	4-11	218 ± 1 (n=11)	59.3 ± 4.8	61.7 ± 5.1	65.2 ± 5.6
		63-90	210 ± 10 (n=14)	68.5 ± 5.1	71.2 ± 5.4	75.0 ± 6.0
		90-125	177 ± 6 (n=22)	58.3 ± 3.8	60.6 ± 4.1	63.8 ± 4.5
PRI 1.11	295	4-11	248 ± 1 (n=11)	72.8 ± 6.0	71.5 ± 5.8	75.5 ± 6.4
		63-90	243 ± 9 (n=10)	85.0 ± 6.0	83.5 ± 5.8	87.9 ± 6.5
		90-125	235 ± 13 (n=12)	83.0 ± 6.7	81.5 ± 6.5	85.8 ± 7.2
PRI 1.12	375	4-11	283 ± 3 (n=10)	94.2 ± 7.7	89.5 ± 7.1	94.5 ± 7.8
		63-90	313 ± 15 (n=10)	123 ± 10	117 ± 9	123 ± 10
		90-125	280 ± 11 (n=10)	111 ± 8	106 ± 8	111 ± 8

Table S2. Roxolany, Ukraine. Equivalent doses (ED), dosimetry measurements and OSL ages. Weighted OSL ages are calculated according to **Aitken (1985)**. Water content estimation was based on the difference between the ‘as found’ and oven-dried weight of the material. The uncertainties associated with luminescence and dosimetry data are random. The uncertainties associated with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. The relative systematic errors taken into account include: 2% beta source calibration, 3% conversion factors, 5% attenuation and etching factors, 3% gamma spectrometer calibration, 50% a-value correction, 15 % cosmic radiation, 25 % water content. All the errors correspond to 1σ . n denotes the number of accepted aliquots.

Sample code	Depth (cm)	Water content (%)	ED (Gy)			U-Ra (Bq/kg)	Th (Bq/kg)	K (Bq/kg)	Total random error (%)			Total systematic error (%)			Total dose rate (Gy/ka)			Age (ka)			
			4-11 μm	63-90 μm	90-125 μm				4-11 μm	63-90 μm	90-125 μm	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	90-125 μm	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	90-125 μm	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	90-125 μm	Weighted quartz ages (ka)
ROX 1.1	31	8	15.6 \pm 0.3 _{n=10}	11.8 \pm 0.5 _{n=9}	15.5 \pm 0.9 _{n=8}	34.9 \pm 0.6	27.3 \pm 0.8	384 \pm 15	2.6	4.6	6.1	8	5.7	5.7	2.94 \pm 0.05	2.48 \pm 0.05	2.45 \pm 0.05	5.3\pm0.5	4.8\pm0.4	6.3\pm0.5	5.3\pm0.4
ROX 1.2	47	9.4	16.2 \pm 0.2 _{n=10}	10.3 \pm 0.5 _{n=10}	12.8 \pm 0.8 _{n=10}	38.5 \pm 2.5	36.0 \pm 1.2	435 \pm 17	2.6	5.4	6.7	8.3	5.9	5.9	3.32 \pm 0.07	2.78 \pm 0.06	2.75 \pm 0.06	4.9\pm0.4	3.7\pm0.3	4.7\pm0.4	4.2\pm0.3
ROX 1.3	53	10.6	28.1 \pm 0.5 _{n=10}	22.2 \pm 1.0 _{n=18}	23.5 \pm 1.0 _{n=15}	37.8 \pm 1.2	36.9 \pm 0.7	409 \pm 16	5.3	6.4	6.3	8.6	6.1	6.0	3.19 \pm 0.16	2.66 \pm 0.12	2.64 \pm 0.12	8.8\pm0.9	8.3\pm0.7	8.9\pm0.8	8.6\pm0.7
ROX 1.4	68	11.1	41.6 \pm 0.5 _{n=10}	38.1 \pm 1.1 _{n=14}	38.0 \pm 1.0 _{n=20}	36.0 \pm 0.5	38.0 \pm 0.2	333 \pm 16	2.1	3.4	3.4	9	6.1	6.1	2.92 \pm 0.05	2.42 \pm 0.05	2.39 \pm 0.04	14.3\pm1.3	15.8\pm1.1	15.9\pm1.1	15.4\pm1.1
ROX 1.5	87	9.3	49.9 \pm 0.9 _{n=7}	48.0 \pm 1.3 _{n=9}	41.2 \pm 1.3 _{n=13}	35.4 \pm 2.0	27.3 \pm 0.6	465 \pm 16	2.7	3.4	3.8	7.8	6.0	6.0	3.12 \pm 0.06	2.65 \pm 0.05	2.62 \pm 0.05	16\pm1.3	18.1\pm1.2	15.7\pm1.1	16.6\pm1.1
ROX 1.6	107	8.6	58.0 \pm 0.5 _{n=7}	54.6 \pm 2.1 _{n=14}	43.1 \pm 2.7 _{n=7}	37.6 \pm 1.2	35.8 \pm 1.3	404 \pm 14	2.0	4.3	6.5	8.4	5.8	5.8	3.19 \pm 0.06	2.67 \pm 0.05	2.63 \pm 0.05	18.2\pm1.6	20.5\pm1.5	16.4\pm1.4	18.3\pm1.2
ROX 1.7	137	8.6	65.8 \pm 1.7 _{n=7}	57.5 \pm 1.5 _{n=8}	53.7 \pm 1.6 _{n=12}	38.4 \pm 0.8	37.5 \pm 0.4	391 \pm 15	3.0	3.1	3.4	8.6	5.8	5.8	3.2 \pm 0.05	2.66 \pm 0.05	2.63 \pm 0.05	20.6\pm1.4	21.6\pm1.4	20.4\pm1.4	21\pm1.4

Table S3. Mircea Voda, Romania. Summary of the equivalent doses, radionuclide activities, calculated dose rates and optical ages. Weighted OSL ages are calculated according to **Aitken (1985)**. Water content estimation was based on the difference between the ‘as found’ and oven-dried weight of the material. Beta attenuation and etching factor used for 63-90 μm 0.94 ± 0.050 while adopted alpha efficiency factor was 0.04 ± 0.02 . The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the alpha, beta and gamma radiations as well as the contribution from the cosmic radiation. The uncertainties associated with luminescence and dosimetry data are random. The uncertainties associated with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. The relative systematic errors taken into account include: 2% beta source calibration, 3% conversion factors, 5% attenuation and etching factors, 3% gamma spectrometer calibration, 50% a-value correction, 15 % cosmic radiation, 25 % water content. All the errors correspond to 1σ . n denotes the number of accepted aliquots.

Sample code	Depth (m)	Water content (%)	De (Gy)		^{238}U - ^{226}Ra (Bq/kg)	^{232}Th (Bq/kg)	^{40}K (Bq/kg)	Total random error (%)		Total systematic error (%)		Total dose rate (Gy/ka)		Age (ka)		
			4-11 μm	63-90 μm				4-11 μm	63-90 μm	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	Weighted quartz ages (ka)
2MV 40	0.4	20 \pm 5	15.4 \pm 0.2n=10	12.9 \pm 1.5 n=19	41 \pm 0.4	37 \pm 2	381 \pm 16	2.3	11.8	9.9	7.6	2.91 \pm 0.05	3.44 \pm 0.05	5.3 \pm 0.5	5.3 \pm 0.5	
2MV 50	0.5		20.3 \pm 0.3n=10	17.3 \pm 1.9 n=20	42 \pm 0.8	38 \pm 2	414 \pm 17	2.7	11.2	9.9	7.6	3.05 \pm 0.07	2.55 \pm 0.06	6.7 \pm 0.7	6.8 \pm 0.9	6.7 \pm 0.6
2MV 60	0.6		23.6 \pm 0.5n=10	22.1 \pm 1.6 n=21	38 \pm 1.2	47 \pm 1	427 \pm 16	2.7	7.4	9.9	7.6	3.15 \pm 0.05	2.64 \pm 0.05	7.5 \pm 0.8	8.4 \pm 0.9	7.9 \pm 0.7
2MV 70	0.7		25.6 \pm 0.3n=10	26.6 \pm 2.1 n=16	40 \pm 0.8	35 \pm 1	393 \pm 17	2.1	8.1	9.9	7.6	2.88 \pm 0.05	2.41 \pm 0.05	8.9 \pm 0.9	11.0 \pm 1.2	9.6 \pm 0.9
2MV 80	0.8		31.2 \pm 0.4n=10	36.4 \pm 2.9 n=18	39 \pm 1	37 \pm 0.3	372 \pm 16	2.0	8.2	10.0	7.6	2.81 \pm 0.05	2.35 \pm 0.05	11.1 \pm 1.1	15.5 \pm 1.7	12 \pm 1
2MV 90	0.9		35.9 \pm 0.6n=10	36.0 \pm 2.5 n=20	39 \pm 0.5	37 \pm 1.3	369 \pm 16	2.5	7.2	10.0	7.6	2.77 \pm 0.05	2.32 \pm 0.05	12.9 \pm 1.3	15.5 \pm 1.6	14 \pm 1
MV 2.1	0.93		28.3 \pm 0.6n=10	36.1 \pm 2.0 n=22	35 \pm 0.6	34 \pm 1	396 \pm 13	2.3	5.8	9.7	7.6	2.75 \pm 0.04	2.31 \pm 0.04	14.0 \pm 1.4	15.6 \pm 1.5	15 \pm 1
MV 2.2	0.99		51.7 \pm 0.6n=10	53.6 \pm 2.6 n=23	38 \pm 2	35 \pm 1	419 \pm 15	2.2	5.2	9.7	7.7	2.88 \pm 0.05	2.42 \pm 0.05	18.0 \pm 1.8	22.1 \pm 2.1	20 \pm 2
MV 2.3	1.23		51.2 \pm 0.9n=10	62.1 \pm 3.0 n=20	37 \pm 2	37 \pm 2	389 \pm 12	2.8	5.3	9.9	7.6	2.81 \pm 0.06	2.53 \pm 0.05	18.2 \pm 1.9	26.4 \pm 2.5	21 \pm 2
MV 2.4	1.35		46.8 \pm 0.8n=10	60.8 \pm 3.8 n=20	42 \pm 2	35 \pm 0.3	403 \pm 12	2.2	6.4	9.9	7.7	2.92 \pm 0.04	2.44 \pm 0.04	16.1 \pm 1.6	24.9 \pm 2.5	19 \pm 2
MV 2.5	1.47		59.7 \pm 1.0n=10	79.0 \pm 4.1 n=21	41 \pm 1	34 \pm 1	393 \pm 13	2.3	5.5	9.9	7.7	2.85 \pm 0.05	2.39 \pm 0.04	20.9 \pm 2.1	33.1 \pm 3.1	22 \pm 2
MV 2.6	1.67		67.4 \pm 0.6n=10	86.9 \pm 3.5 n=20	43 \pm 2	36 \pm 1	385 \pm 12	2.0	4.4	10.1	7.7	2.91 \pm 0.05	2.42 \pm 0.04	22.8 \pm 2.3	35.9 \pm 3.2	27 \pm 3

Table S4. Râmnicu Sărat, Romania. Equivalent doses (ED), dosimetry measurements and OSL ages. Water content estimation was based on the difference between the ‘as found’ and oven-dried weight of the material. The uncertainties associated with luminescence and dosimetry data are random. The uncertainties associated with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. The relative systematic errors taken into account include: 2% beta source calibration, 3% conversion factors, 5% attenuation and etching factors, 3% gamma spectrometer calibration, 50% a-value correction, 15 % cosmic radiation, 25 % water content. All the errors correspond to 1σ . n denotes the number of accepted aliquots.

Sample code	Depth (cm)	Water content (%)	Grain size (μm)	De (Gy)	^{238}U - ^{226}Ra (Bq/kg)	^{232}Th (Bq/kg)	^{40}K (Bq/kg)	Total dose rate (Gy/ka)	Total random error (%)	Total systematic error (%)	Age (ka)
RS 050	50	4%	63-90	5.2 ± 0.6 _{n=11}	33.6 ± 1.7	32.1 ± 0.8	380.8 ± 11.9	2.61 ± 0.05	11.7	5.4	2.0 ± 0.3
RS 060	60	2%		6.9 ± 0.4 _{n=11}	35.7 ± 2.2	35.5 ± 0.4	457.9 ± 13.6	3.02 ± 0.06	6.1	5.4	2.3 ± 0.2
RS 070	70	9%		7.3 ± 0.3 _{n=9}	35.8 ± 1.0	34.2 ± 1.9	468.4 ± 13.9	2.79 ± 0.05	4.5	5.9	2.6 ± 0.2
RS 080	80	5%		16.8 ± 0.5 _{n=11}	34.6 ± 1.4	33.3 ± 1.7	446.5 ± 11.9	2.81 ± 0.05	3.5	5.5	6.0 ± 0.4
RS 090	90	2%		23.4 ± 0.7 _{n=18}	37.6 ± 0.2	38.4 ± 1.3	489.2 ± 15.1	3.18 ± 0.05	3.4	5.4	7.4 ± 0.5
RS 100	100	6%		29.7 ± 1.0 _{n=20}	35.8 ± 1.6	37.5 ± 1.4	459.0 ± 12.9	2.90 ± 0.05	3.8	5.6	10.3 ± 0.7
RS 110	110	6%		32.7 ± 2.1 _{n=11}	36.4 ± 1.4	39.6 ± 0.6	482.9 ± 13.4	3.01 ± 0.05	6.6	5.6	10.9 ± 1.0
RS 120	120	6%		37.1 ± 1.4 _{n=19}	37.0 ± 1.7	41.3 ± 3.2	450.0 ± 15.3	2.95 ± 0.08	4.6	5.6	12.6 ± 0.9
RS 130	130	5%		36.0 ± 1.9 _{n=14}	36.7 ± 1.3	38.1 ± 1.8	447.7 ± 15.9	2.92 ± 0.06	5.7	5.5	12.4 ± 1.0
RS 140	140	9%		42.4 ± 1.7 _{n=15}	32.5 ± 2.4	33.6 ± 3.0	367.8 ± 14.7	2.41 ± 0.07	5.0	5.9	17.6 ± 1.4
RS 150	150	6%		50.4 ± 1.9 _{n=15}	33.9 ± 1.4	35.4 ± 1.4	475.8 ± 18.1	2.86 ± 0.06	4.4	5.6	17.6 ± 1.3
RS 160	160	6%		37.6 ± 1.3 _{n=14}	35.9 ± 3.3	35.5 ± 3.0	394.2 ± 15.6	2.66 ± 0.08	4.7	5.6	14.2 ± 1.0

Table S5. Equivalent doses (ED), dosimetry measurements and OSL ages for Mosorin samples, Serbia. Weighted OSL ages are calculated according to **Aitken (1985)**. Equivalent doses obtained for polymineral fine (4-11 μm) grains were determined using the post-IR IRSL₂₉₀ protocol. The residual doses for samples MVS 3, 4 and 7 were measured after 4 h bleaching in the solar simulator; the signal collected during the initial ~ 2 s of stimulation, less a background from the last 20 s was used for calculations;*an average residual dose was calculated using the residual doses measured for samples MVS 3, 4 and 7 and was subtracted from the equivalent doses obtained for the rest of the samples; Water content estimation was based on the difference between the ‘as found’ and oven-dried weight of the material. The uncertainties associated with luminescence and dosimetry data are random. The uncertainties associated with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. The relative systematic errors taken into account include: 2% beta source calibration, 3% conversion factors, 5% attenuation and etching factors, 3% gamma spectrometer calibration, 50% a-value correction, 15 % cosmic radiation, 25 % water content. All the errors correspond to 1σ . n denotes the number of accepted aliquots.

Sample code	Depth (cm)	Water content (%)	ED (Gy)			Residual dose (Gy) 4-11 μm pfg	ED after residual dose subtraction (Gy) 4-11 μm pfg	²³⁸ U, ²²⁶ Ra (Bq/kg)	²³² Th (Bq/kg)	⁴⁰ K (Bq/kg)	Total random error (%)			Total systematic error (%)			Total dose rate (Gy/ka)			Age (ka)			Weighted quartz ages
			4-11 μm quartz	63-90 μm quartz	4-11 μm pfg						4-11 μm quartz	63-90 μm quartz	4-11 μm pfg	4-11 μm quartz	63-90 μm quartz	4-11 μm pfg	4-11 μm quartz	63-90 μm quartz	4-11 μm pfg	4-11 μm quartz	63-90 μm quartz	4-11 μm pfg	
MVS 1	15	3.1	5.3 \pm 0.2 _{n=7}	2.3 \pm 0.4 _{n=8}	-	-	-	38.6 \pm 0.3	39.9 \pm 0.4	452.0 \pm 6	5.4	17.4	-	8.1	5.5	-	3.76 \pm 0.15	3.15 \pm 0.02	-	1.4 \pm 0.1	0.7 \pm 0.1	-	1.2 \pm 0.1
MVS 2	15	4.4	5.0 \pm 0.3 _{n=7}	3.7 \pm 1.2 _{n=5}	-	-	-	31.7 \pm 0.3	36.3 \pm 0.8	452.0 \pm 6	7.3	32.4	-	7.7	5.5	-	3.44 \pm 0.14	2.91 \pm 0.02	-	1.5 \pm 0.2	1.3 \pm 0.4	-	
MVS 3	20	1.7	14.4 \pm 0.4 _{n=7}	10.3 \pm 2.3 _{n=8}	57.2 \pm 2.6 _{n=7}	16.3 \pm 0.4	40.9 \pm 2.6	28.7 \pm 0.4	34.6 \pm 0.6	436 \pm 6	5.0	22.3	7.4	7.6	5.6	7.2	3.36 \pm 0.14	2.85 \pm 0.02	3.76 \pm \pm 0.15	4.3 \pm 0.4	3.6 \pm 0.8	10.9 \pm 1.1	4.1 \pm 0.4
MVS 4	30	5.0	29.8 \pm 0.3 _{n=17}	36.0 \pm 2.5 _{n=8}	77.6 \pm 3.1 _{n=6}	15.4 \pm 0.6	62.2 \pm 3.1	29.4 \pm 0.3	35.2 \pm 1.0	404 \pm 5	4.1	7.0	6.2	7.7	5.5	7.3	3.00 \pm 0.12	2.64 \pm 0.02	3.37 \pm 0.13	9.9 \pm 0.9	13.6 \pm 1.2	18.5 \pm 1.9	10.9 \pm 0.8
MVS 5	30	8.6	31.9 \pm 0.4 _{n=14}	27.9 \pm 2.4 _{n=9}	80.1 \pm 1.5 _{n=6}	16.8 \pm 0.1	63.2 \pm 1.8	29.7 \pm 0.6	33.0 \pm 0.7	418 \pm 7	4.2	8.7	4.7	7.6	5.6	7.2	3.04 \pm 0.12	2.57 \pm 0.03	3.40 \pm 0.13	10.5 \pm 0.9	10.8 \pm 1.1	18.8 \pm 1.6	
MVS 6	45	8.8	36.7 \pm 0.6 _{n=14}	34.2 \pm 1.7 _{n=10}	73.1 \pm 1.7 _{n=5}	16.8 \pm 0.1	56.2 \pm 1.9	29.4 \pm 0.1	34.6 \pm 1.1	405 \pm 5	4.3	5.05	5.0	7.8	5.5	7.3	3.01 \pm 0.12	2.54 \pm 0.02	3.37 \pm 0.13	12.2 \pm 1.8	13.5 \pm 1.0	16.7 \pm 1.5	13.5 \pm 0.9
MVS 7	45	10.1	39.9 \pm 0.3 _{n=14}	34.6 \pm 1.3 _{n=10}	84.6 \pm 3.6 _{n=7}	18.8 \pm 0.4	65.9 \pm 3.6	29.6 \pm 0.3	34.9 \pm 0.8	383 \pm 7	3.9	3.9	6.6	7.9	5.5	7.3	2.91 \pm 0.11	2.45 \pm 0.02	3.27 \pm 0.12	13.7 \pm 1.2	14.1 \pm 0.9	20.1 \pm 1.9	
MVS 8	60	9.1	41.4 \pm 0.8 _{n=14}	39.0 \pm 1.8 _{n=6}	83.4 \pm 2.9 _{n=6}	16.8 \pm 0.1	66.6 \pm 3.1	37.0 \pm 0.5	37.1 \pm 0.9	421 \pm 6	4.3	4.7	5.9	8.1	5.6	7.5	3.28 \pm 0.13	2.75 \pm 0.02	3.71 \pm 0.13	12.6 \pm 1.6	14.2 \pm 1.0	18.0 \pm 1.7	13.7 \pm 0.9
MVS 9	60	7.8	38.9 \pm 1.0 _{n=5}	38.3 \pm 2.2 _{n=13}	76.1 \pm 1.5 _{n=5}	16.8 \pm 0.1	59.2 \pm 1.8	27.6 \pm 0.1	34.9 \pm 0.3	396 \pm 7	4.8	5.8	4.9	7.8	5.5	7.3	2.96 \pm 0.12	2.49 \pm 0.02	3.32 \pm 0.13	13.1 \pm 1.2	15.3 \pm 1.2	17.8 \pm 1.6	
MVS 10	75	9.2	41.9 \pm 1.4 _{n=10}	34.4 \pm 3.0 _{n=9}	73.2 \pm 4.1 _{n=7}	16.8 \pm 0.1	56.4 \pm 4.3	32.3 \pm 0.3	35.5 \pm 0.9	396 \pm 6	5.1	8.8	8.5	7.9	5.5	7.4	3.04 \pm 0.12	2.55 \pm 0.02	3.43 \pm 0.13	13.8 \pm 1.3	13.5 \pm 1.4	16.5 \pm 1.9	14.6 \pm 1.1
MVS 11	75	8.8	44.1 \pm 0.6 _{n=10}	38.8 \pm 2.7 _{n=7}	83.9 \pm 4.1 _{n=6}	16.8 \pm 0.1	67.1 \pm 4.2	29.9 \pm 0.5	36.1 \pm 0.5	385 \pm 6	4.2	7.0	7.3	7.9	5.5	7.4	2.88 \pm 0.11	2.42 \pm 0.02	3.24 \pm 0.12	15.3 \pm 1.4	16.0 \pm 1.4	20.7 \pm 2.1	

Table S6. Smederevo, Serbia. Summary of preliminary SAR OSL ages determined on 63-90 μm quartz and dosimetry data. The uncertainties associated with the luminescence and dosimetry data are random; the uncertainties mentioned with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. Activities were measured on well detector by gamma spectrometry and annual dose rates were determined using the conversion factors tabulated by **Guérin et al. (2011)**. $10\pm 2.5\%$ water content was considered. The beta attenuation and etching factors used for 63-90 μm quartz were 0.94 ± 0.050 (**Mejdahl, 1979**). The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the beta and gamma radiations. The contribution of cosmic radiation was taken into account and calculated according to **Prescott and Hutton (1994)**. For coarse quartz grains an internal dose rate of 0.01 ± 0.002 Gy/ka was considered (**Vandenberghé et al., 2008**).

Sample code	Depth (m)	Water content (%)	De (Gy)	^{238}U - ^{226}Ra (Bq/kg)	^{232}Th (Bq/kg)	^{40}K (Bq/kg)	Annual dose rate (Gy/ka)	Random error (%)	Systematic error (%)	Age (ka)
SM-20	0.2		26 ± 2 $n=4$	50 ± 1	50 ± 2	459 ± 18	3.34 ± 0.07	7.9	6	8 ± 1
SM-40	0.4		44 ± 6 $n=6$	56 ± 1	62 ± 2	659 ± 19	4.20 ± 0.07	13.7	6.1	11 ± 2
SM-50	0.5		50 ± 2 $n=7$	46 ± 2	48 ± 2	476 ± 17	3.25 ± 0.07	4.5	6	15 ± 1
SM-60	0.6		58 ± 3 $n=16$	42 ± 2	41 ± 2	382 ± 15	2.76 ± 0.06	5.6	6	21 ± 2
SM-70	0.7	10 ± 2.5	92 ± 7 $n=9$	36 ± 1	37 ± 0	351 ± 16	2.51 ± 0.05	3.8	5.9	37 ± 3
SM-80	0.8		90 ± 11 $n=9$	48 ± 2	42 ± 2	356 ± 16	2.81 ± 0.06	12.4	5.9	32 ± 4
SM-90	0.9		102 ± 5 $n=15$	49 ± 2	41 ± 1	381 ± 16	2.88 ± 0.06	5.3	6	35 ± 3
SM-100	1		133 ± 8 $n=10$	46 ± 1	43 ± 2	453 ± 16	3.07 ± 0.06	6.3	6	43 ± 4
SM-150	1.5		149 ± 17 $n=6$	41 ± 2	52 ± 2	484 ± 16	3.19 ± 0.06	11.6	6	47 ± 6

Table S7. Caoxian, Chinese Loess Plateau. Summary of preliminary SAR OSL ages determined on 63-90 μm quartz and dosimetry data. The uncertainties associated with the luminescence and dosimetry data are random; the uncertainties mentioned with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. Activities were measured on well detector by gamma spectrometry and annual dose rates were determined using the conversion factors tabulated by **Guérin et al. (2011)**. Water content estimation was based on the difference between the ‘as found’ and oven-dried weight of the material. The beta attenuation and etching factors used for 63-90 μm quartz were 0.94 ± 0.050 (**Mejdahl, 1979**). The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the beta and gamma radiations. The contribution of cosmic radiation was taken into account and calculated according to **Prescott and Hutton (1994)**. For coarse quartz grains an internal dose rate of 0.01 ± 0.002 Gy/ka was considered (**Vandenberghe et al., 2008**).

Sample code	Depth (m)	Water content (%)	ED(Gy)	^{238}U - ^{226}Ra (Bq/kg)	^{232}Th (Bq/kg)	^{40}K (Bq/kg)	Annual dose rate (Gy/ka)	Random error (%)	Systematic error (%)	Age (ka)
CX 1.5	0.73	15 \pm 4	$0.9 \pm 0.1_{n=10}$	35 ± 1	42 ± 1	456 ± 15	2.82 ± 0.05	9	6.7	0.32 ± 0.04
CX 1.4	1.40		$2.5 \pm 0.2_{n=12}$	33 ± 2	41 ± 2	478 ± 15	2.79 ± 0.06	8.3	6.7	0.90 ± 0.10
CX 1.3	2.08		$13.4 \pm 0.3_{n=13}$	36 ± 1	38 ± 1	520 ± 16	2.89 ± 0.05	2.8	6.8	4.6 ± 0.3
CX 1.2	2.28		$16 \pm 1_{n=13}$	37 ± 1	44 ± 3	505 ± 16	2.96 ± 0.06	4.4	6.7	5.3 ± 0.4
CX 1.1	2.48		$22 \pm 1_{n=13}$	35 ± 1	39 ± 0	543 ± 16	2.95 ± 0.04	4.4	6.8	7 ± 1
CX 1.0	2.53		$19 \pm 1_{n=12}$	33 ± 2	40 ± 2	529 ± 15	2.88 ± 0.05	4.2	6.8	6 ± 1
CX 2.5	2.73		$30 \pm 2_{n=15}$	38 ± 2	39 ± 2	477 ± 17	2.81 ± 0.06	6.1	6.8	11 ± 1
CX 2.4	2.88		$34 \pm 1_{n=12}$	35 ± 1	40 ± 1	522 ± 18	2.88 ± 0.05	4.2	6.8	12 ± 1
CX 2.3	3.00		$42 \pm 3_{n=6}$	35 ± 2	37 ± 2	470 ± 14	2.71 ± 0.05	6.7	6.8	15 ± 1
CX 2.2	3.18		$41 \pm 2_{n=14}$	37 ± 2	39 ± 3	520 ± 17	2.90 ± 0.06	4.9	6.8	14 ± 1
CX 2.1	3.45		$42 \pm 2_{n=9}$	36 ± 1	39 ± 2	494 ± 15	2.81 ± 0.05	5.8	6.8	15 ± 1
CX 2.0	3.90		$45 \pm 2_{n=9}$	34 ± 2	37 ± 2	505 ± 15	2.76 ± 0.05	4.9	6.8	16 ± 1

Table S8. Baicaoyuan, Chinese Loess Plateau. Equivalent doses (ED), dosimetry measurements and OSL ages. Weighted OSL ages are calculated according to **Aitken (1985)**. Water content estimation was based on the difference between the ‘as found’ and oven-dried weight of the material. Beta attenuation and etching factor used for 63-90 μm 0.94 ± 0.050 while adopted alpha efficiency factor was 0.04 ± 0.02 . The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the alpha, beta and gamma radiations as well as the contribution from the cosmic radiation. The uncertainties associated with luminescence and dosimetry data are random. The uncertainties associated with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. The relative systematic errors taken into account include: 2% beta source calibration, 3% conversion factors, 5% attenuation and etching factors, 3% gamma spectrometer calibration, 50% a-value correction, 15 % cosmic radiation, 25 % water content. All the errors correspond to 1σ . n denotes the number of accepted aliquots.

Sample code	Depth(m)	Water content(%)	De (Gy)		^{238}U - ^{226}Ra (Bq/kg)	^{232}Th (Bq/kg)	^{40}K (Bq/kg)	Total random error (%)		Total systematic error (%)		Total dose rate (Gy/ka)		Age (ka)		
			4-11 μm	63-90 μm				4-11 μm	63-90 μm	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	Weighted quartz ages (ka)
BCY 1.9	0.43	15 \pm 4	2.5 \pm 0.2 _{n=8}	2 \pm 0.2 _{n=10}	36 \pm 1	42 \pm 1	582 \pm 17	8.1	10.1	8.4	6.7	3.77 \pm 0.05	3.22 \pm 0.05	0.7 \pm 0.1	0.6 \pm 0.1	0.6\pm0.1
BCY 1.8	0.78		26 \pm 0.2 _{n=8}	23 \pm 1 _{n=10}	36 \pm 1	39 \pm 2	535 \pm 14	1.8	4.3	8.4	6.7	3.51 \pm 0.06	2.99 \pm 0.05	7.4 \pm 0.6	7.50.6	7.5\pm0.6
BCY 1.7	0.93		31 \pm 1 _{n=10}	26 \pm 1 _{n=10}	37 \pm 1	41 \pm 1	547 \pm 16	2.4	3.1	8.5	6.7	3.61 \pm 0.05	3.07 \pm 0.05	8.7 \pm 0.8	8.5 \pm 0.6	8.6\pm0.7
BCY 1.6	1.03		37 \pm 1 _{n=10}	32 \pm 1 _{n=10}	34 \pm 1	38 \pm 1	483 \pm 14	2.6	3.2	8.5	6.7	3.28 \pm 0.05	2.79 \pm 0.04	11 \pm 1	11.5 \pm 0.9	11.4\pm0.9
BCY 1.5	1.13		41 \pm 1 _{n=10}	37 \pm 1 _{n=10}	32 \pm 1	37 \pm 1	466 \pm 15	3.3	3.7	8.5	6.7	3.17 \pm 0.05	2.70 \pm 0.04	13 \pm 1	14 \pm 1	13\pm1
BCY 1.4	1.18		41 \pm 1 _{n=10}	37 \pm 1 _{n=10}	36 \pm 1	40 \pm 1	510 \pm 14	2.1	3.9	8.6	6.7	3.43 \pm 0.05	2.91 \pm 0.04	12 \pm 1	13 \pm 1	12\pm1
BCY 1.3	1.30		45 \pm 2 _{n=10}	39 \pm 1 _{n=13}	36 \pm 1	41 \pm 1	511 \pm 15	4.1	3.9	8.6	6.7	3.47 \pm 0.05	2.94 \pm 0.05	13 \pm 1	13 \pm 1	13\pm1
BCY 1.2	1.40		49 \pm 1 _{n=55}	42 \pm 1 _{n=51}	35 \pm 2	39 \pm 2	505 \pm 13	2.0	2.5	8.5	6.7	3.36 \pm 0.06	2.86 \pm 0.05	15 \pm 1	15 \pm 1	15\pm1
BCY 1.1	1.63		49 \pm 1 _{n=10}	43 \pm 1 _{n=11}	32 \pm 1	38 \pm 1	536 \pm 16	3.2	2.4	8.3	6.8	3.36 \pm 0.05	2.87 \pm 0.05	15 \pm 1	15 \pm 1	15\pm1
BCY 1.0	2.08		69 \pm 1 _{n=9}	48 \pm 2 _{n=11}	35 \pm 1	41 \pm 2	561 \pm 15	2.9	3.5	8.5	6.8	3.57 \pm 0.06	3.04 \pm 0.05	19 \pm 2	16 \pm 1	17\pm1

Table S9. Kuma, central Great Plains, Nebraska, USA. Summary of the luminescence and dosimetry data. Weighted OSL ages are calculated according to Aitken (1985). The uncertainties associated with the luminescence and dosimetry data are random; the uncertainties mentioned with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. All uncertainties represent 1σ . Specific activities were measured on Well detector and the ages were determined considering the “as found” water content, with a relative error of 25%; n denotes the number of accepted aliquots; beta attenuation and etching factor used for 63-90 μm and 90-125 μm fractions are 0.94 ± 0.05 and 0.92 ± 0.05 , respectively; adopted alpha efficiency factor was 0.04 ± 0.02 . The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the alpha, beta and gamma radiations as well as the contribution from the cosmic radiation.

Sample code	Depth (m)	Water content as found (%)	Grain size (μm)	De (Gy)	^{238}U - ^{226}Ra (Bq/kg)	^{232}Th (Bq/kg)	^{40}K (Bq/kg)	Total random error (%)	Total systematic error (%)	Total dose rate (Gy/ka)	Age (ka)	Weighted age (ka)
KUM 1.1	0.24	6.4	4-11	37.0 ± 0.4 $n=1$	45 ± 1	48 ± 3	647 ± 19	2.2	7.7	4.61 ± 0.09	8.0 ± 0.6	7.9 ± 0.5
			63-90	31 ± 1 $n=2$				2.7	5.6	3.89 ± 0.07	7.9 ± 0.5	
			90-125	30 ± 1 $n=10$				3.8	5.6	3.85 ± 0.07	7.8 ± 0.5	
KUM 1.2	0.37	5.4	4-11	47 ± 0.4 $n=10$	46 ± 2	44 ± 3	640 ± 19	2.3	7.6	4.54 ± 0.10	10.4 ± 0.8	10.5 ± 0.7
			63-90	42 ± 1 $n=20$				2.8	5.6	3.83 ± 0.08	11.1 ± 0.7	
			90-125	37 ± 1 $n=10$				4.3	5.6	3.79 ± 0.08	9.9 ± 0.7	
KUM 1.3	0.53	2.5	4-11	51 ± 1 $n=10$	41 ± 2	43 ± 2	603 ± 21	2.6	7.5	4.41 ± 0.10	11.6 ± 0.9	12.4 ± 0.8
			63-90	49 ± 1 $n=20$				2.7	5.4	3.72 ± 0.09	13.1 ± 0.8	
			90-125	45 ± 1 $n=10$				3.3	5.4	3.67 ± 0.08	12.3 ± 0.8	
KUM 1.4	0.60	5.4	4-11	53 ± 1 $n=10$	42 ± 3	41 ± 2	607 ± 18	3.0	7.6	4.41 ± 0.09	12.5 ± 1.0	13.5 ± 0.9
			63-90	52 ± 1 $n=22$				2.6	5.6	3.61 ± 0.08	14.5 ± 0.9	
			90-125	47 ± 2 $n=10$				3.8	5.6	3.57 ± 0.07	13.2 ± 0.9	
KUM 1.5	0.67	5.0	4-11	58 ± 1 $n=10$	42 ± 3	45 ± 1	623 ± 16	2.0	7.6	4.41 ± 0.08	13.2 ± 1.0	14.0 ± 0.9
			63-90	52 ± 1 $n=19$				2.4	5.6	3.73 ± 0.06	14.1 ± 0.9	
			90-125	53 ± 1 $n=10$				2.7	5.5	3.68 ± 0.06	14.4 ± 0.9	
KUM 1.6	0.76	5.1	4-11	58 ± 1 $n=10$	44 ± 3	43 ± 1	603 ± 17	2.1	7.7	4.34 ± 0.08	13.3 ± 1.1	13.9 ± 0.9
			63-90	53 ± 1 $n=20$				2.4	5.6	3.65 ± 0.07	14.4 ± 0.9	
			90-125	50 ± 1 $n=10$				2.5	5.5	3.61 ± 0.07	13.7 ± 0.8	
KUM 1.7	1.02	4.1	4-11	42 ± 1 $n=10$	49 ± 2	43 ± 1	637 ± 16	2.3	7.7	4.62 ± 0.06	9.1 ± 0.7	13.1 ± 0.8
			63-90	54 ± 1 $n=19$				2.7	5.5	3.88 ± 0.06	13.9 ± 0.8	
			90-125	47 ± 2 $n=10$				4.3	5.5	3.83 ± 0.06	12.3 ± 0.9	

KUM 1.8	2.00	6.6	4-11	$61 \pm 1_{n=10}$	43 ± 2	40 ± 1	672 ± 19	2.6	7.5	4.36 ± 0.08	14.0 ± 1.1	14.7 ± 0.9
			63-90	$56 \pm 1_{n=17}$				2.7	5.7	3.71 ± 0.07	15.1 ± 1.0	
			90-125	$54 \pm 1_{n=10}$				2.9	5.7	3.66 ± 0.07	14.7 ± 0.9	